

Molecular Dynamics Modelling of Thermostatic Properties of Nanoparticles

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

Master of Technology

in

Nanotechnology

by

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June 2020

Certificate

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Abstract

Lack of consistency and reproducibility in the experimental thermal properties of nanofluids are causing limitations in the advancement of this field. The origin of such anomalies remains unclear. To address these issues, and from the need for uniform description at the molecular level, this thesis studies various nano-structures (of different sizes and shapes) with free surfaces. To perform the studies all-atom classical molecular dynamics is used. Using the "soft" phonon description of the liquid-like layers formed on the surfaces, several structural and dynamic properties were found to be strongly linked to the surface phonons. With the classical description of collective vibration amplitudes at the surface layers, universal criteria of phase transition are proposed. The specific heat increase is correlated to the decrease of the interface density and to the corresponding appearance of thermal modes able to store more efficiently the heat, the softer surface phonons, which, clearly, are not present in bulk systems. From the results, a generic criterion for the heat capacity enhancement in solid nanoparticles is suggested, with a scaling law for planar surfaces.

Contents

Acknowledgment	i
Abstract	iii
Contents	v
List of Figures	ix
List of Tables	xvii
1 Introduction	1
2 State of the Art	5
2.1 Nanofluids for Heat Storage - Present Scenario	5
2.2 Thermal Properties of LJ Nanoparticles	6
2.3 Phase Transition of LJ Nanoparticles	6
3 Theory and Conceptual Details	9
3.1 Classical Molecular Dynamics	9
3.1.1 Thermodynamics Ensemble Constraints	10
3.1.2 Interatomic Interaction Potentials	12
3.1.3 Integration Algorithms	13
3.2 Physical Quantities of Interest from MD Simulation	16
3.2.1 Energy	16
3.2.2 Temperature	16
3.2.3 Pressure	17
3.2.4 Pair Correlation Function	17
3.2.5 Specific Heat	17

3.2.6	Mean Squared Displacement	18
3.2.7	Density Profile	18
3.3	Reduced Units	19
3.4	Data Analysis Methods	19
3.5	Tools and Implementation	23
4	Case Study 1 - Nano-Slab	25
4.1	Simulation Details	25
4.2	Results	27
4.2.1	Structural Analysis	27
4.2.2	Phase Transition Analysis	31
4.2.3	Specific Heat Analysis	38
4.3	Discussion	41
5	Case Study 2 - Nano-Sphere	43
5.1	Simulation Details	43
5.2	Results	45
5.2.1	Structural Analysis	45
5.2.2	Phase Transition Analysis	49
5.2.3	Specific Heat Analysis	56
5.3	Discussion	57
6	Case Study 3 - Hollow Nano-Shell	59
6.1	Simulation Details	59
6.2	Results	61
6.2.1	Structural Analysis	61
6.2.2	Phase Transition Analysis	64
6.2.3	Specific Heat Analysis	64
6.3	Discussion	67
7	Conclusions and Future Scope	69
	Bibliography	70

Appendix	82
7.1 LAMMPS inputs scripts	83
7.1.1 Generation of initial atomic positions - Nano-slab	83
7.1.2 Generation of initial atomic positions - Nano-sphere	84
7.1.3 Generation of initial atomic positions - Hollow nano-shell	84
7.1.4 Thermal cycling of Nano-slab	86
7.1.5 Thermal cycling of Nano-sphere	87
7.1.6 Thermal cycling of Hollow nano-shell	89
7.1.7 Production run of Nano-slab	90
7.1.8 Production run of Nano-sphere	91
7.1.9 Production run of Hollow nano-shell	92
7.2 Data analysis codes in FORTRAN90	93
7.2.1 Local & cumulative density profile - Nano-slab	93
7.2.2 Local & cumulative density profile - Nano-sphere & hollow nano-shell	98
7.2.3 Amplitude of atomic vibrations - Nano-slab	104

List of Figures

1.1	Different types of possible thermal storage materials. TES system can be distinguished in three types by the mechanism of storing heat. In sensible heat storage systems, nanofluids, being the predominant material to store heat in a CSP, dominated research in recent years. Sensible-latent heat storage system is also in the forefront of innovation owing to higher energy storage density of such corresponding materials.	2
3.1	A typical flow-chart of MD simulation	11
3.2	The Lennard-Jones 12-6 potential approximates the intermolecular interactions of two atoms due to Pauli repulsion and Van der Waals attraction between non-ionic particles. [Image copied from https://glossary.periodni.com/glossary.php?en=Lennard-Jones+potential (Generalic 2018)]	13
3.3	Phase diagram of the LJ system. Reprinted from (Travesset 2014), with the permission of AIP Publishing.	14
3.4	Potential energy behaviour of a nanosystem as a function of temperature. Cyan Square (Empty Square) symbols correspond to step-by-step heating procedure. Solid black line corresponds to the quasi-continuous method. And Orange (Dashed) line is the quartic fit of the quasi-continuous method.	22
4.1	Snapshots of the initial atomic positions of (a) n_{SI1} , (b) n_{SI2} , (c) n_{SI3} , (d) n_{SI4} and (e) n_{SI5} respectively. All samples have free surface in the x direction.	26
4.2	Scheme for preparing initial configuration. Highlighted part represents the final configuration used for obtaining production part of the simulation	27

- 4.3 Cumulative density profile of all n_{sl} samples at $T = 0.01$ (Solid line), $T = 0.15$ (Dashed line) and $T = 0.2$ (Dash-dotted line). Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\Delta/2$ in the abscissa. Black, red, blue, green and orange lines reports of the n_{sl1} , n_{sl2} , n_{sl3} , n_{sl4} and n_{sl5} respectively. 28
- 4.4 Density of the investigated n_{sl} systems as a function of temperature. Red, magenta, blue, yellow and green points are the density of n_{sl1} , n_{sl2} , n_{sl3} , n_{sl4} and n_{sl5} consecutively. 29
- 4.5 Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis of investigated systems. Green colored atoms are inner fcc atoms, maroon colored atoms are surface atoms with unknown local structure of (a) n_{sl1} at $T = 0.01$, (b) n_{sl1} at $T = 0.2$, (c) n_{sl2} at $T = 0.01$, (d) n_{sl2} at $T = 0.2$, (e) n_{sl3} at $T = 0.01$, (f) n_{sl3} at $T = 0.2$, (g) n_{sl4} at $T = 0.01$, (h) n_{sl4} at $T = 0.2$, (i) n_{sl5} at $T = 0.01$, and (j) n_{sl5} at $T = 0.2$ consecutively. Different phonon modes can be seen emerging on the surface 30
- 4.6 Local density profiles of (a) n_{sl5} and (b) n_{sl1} , rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\Delta}{2}$ in the abscissa. Black (dashed) line illustrates the trend at $T = 0.01$ and green (solid) line describes the trend at $T = 0.25$. In the case of n_{sl5} , from the deviation of density from average value, two regions have been identified: Bulk region (yellow), and Surface region (red). Although this consideration is invalid for n_{sl1} - as no bulk layer was present. 32
- 4.7 Trajectories of the flying atoms for (a) n_{sl1} , (b) n_{sl2} , (c) n_{sl3} , (d) n_{sl4} and (e) n_{sl5} individually. Using Ackland-Jones bond-angle method, atoms on the surfaces are marked with maroon color while green colored atoms are inner fcc atoms. Path which the flying atoms follow are depicted with blue line. 33
- 4.8 Snapshots of n_{sl1} two phase non-equilibrium simulation at different temperature range 34

- 4.9 Detailed analysis of solid-to-gas phase transition temperature (T_M) behavior is plotted for different n_{SI} samples and compared with reference bulk. Triangular shaped data-points are T_M value identified from flying atom method. Error bar shows the determined ΔT from the evolution of two-phase non-equilibrium configuration. (a) shows progression of T_M as the slab thickness (Δ) increases. Black dashed line indicates Bulk melting transition temperature $T = 0.56$ at $P = 0.001$. Blue dashed line is for a nearest-neighbor LJ solid model fitted melting temperature $T = 0.5$ at $P = 0$ reported elsewhere (Cowley 1983). In (b) abscissa reports inverse T_M as a function of surface atoms to total atom ratio η in the ordinate. Black and blue squares are denotations of bulk at $P = 0.001$ and $P = 0$ respectively, while red square is the extrapolated T_M of bulk from the linear fit 35
- 4.10 Mean squared displacement (msd) of smallest and largest n_{SI} system, as a function of MD time-steps. Data are shown for T just below T_M and $T = 0.25$ (solid phase) for each nano-system. 36
- 4.11 Normal distribution of probability density function attributed to the surface (soft) phonons and bulk (hard) phonons. Red dashed lines are the average lattice positions at corresponding T , calculated from the x -Cartesian component of the msd. 37
- 4.12 Potential energy (E_{Pot}) of (a) n_{SI1} and (b) n_{SI5} , calculated over temperature range of $0.01 - T_M$ at $P = 0$. E_{Pot} is summed over N 38
- 4.13 Isobaric specific heat (c_p) of n_{SI1} (red), n_{SI2} (green), n_{SI3} (magenta), n_{SI4} (blue) and n_{SI5} (yellow) at $P = 0$, investigated in solid regime. The highest data-point corresponds to the solid-to-gas phase transition (T_M). For comparison, reference bulk data in shown in black. Inset - $c_p(T)$ rescaled over T_M 39
- 5.1 Snapshots of the initial atomic configurations of (a) n_{sp1} , (b) n_{sp2} , (c) n_{sp3} , (d) n_{sp4} and (e) n_{sp5} sequentially. All samples have free surface in all spatial (x, y, z) direction. 43

5.2 Cumulative number density distributions of all n_{sp} samples at $T = 0.15$. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Black, red, blue, green and orange lines report cumulative density profiles of the n_{sp1} , n_{sp2} , n_{sp3} , n_{sp4} and n_{sp5} respectively. 45

5.3 For n_{sp1} , detailed explorations of density profile trends at $T = 0.01$ (black), $T = 0.1$ (red), $T = 0.15$ (blue) and $T = 0.2$ (magenta). (a) Cumulative number density profile corroborates expansion of system with increasing temperature. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. (b) Local density profile rescaled over bulk density as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$. At $T = 0.01$ density peaks are well-defined, whereas with increasing temperature the peaks starts to broaden. 46

5.4 Cumulative number density profiles (red line) $T = 0.3$. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Inset shows deviation from cubic behaviour (blue line) in outer layers. 48

5.5 Local density profiles of n_{sp5} rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Blue (dashed) line illustrates the trend at $T = 0.01$ and red (solid) line describes the trend at $T = 0.3$. From the deviation of density from average value, three regions have been identified; 1 - Bulk region, 2 - Interface region and 3 - Surface region. 49

5.6 Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis of investigated systems. Green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms, blue colored atoms are inner *hcp* atoms and maroon colored atoms are surface atoms with unknown local structure of (a) n_{sp1} at $T = 0.01$, (b) n_{sp1} at $T = 0.2$, (c) n_{sp2} at $T = 0.01$, (d) n_{sp2} at $T = 0.2$, (e) n_{sp5} at $T = 0.01$ and (f) n_{sp5} at $T = 0.2$ consecutively. Different phonon modes can be seen emerging on the surface 50

5.7	Trajectories of the flying atoms. Using Ackland-Jones bond-angle method, atoms on the surfaces are marked with maroon color, blue colored atoms are inner <i>hcp</i> atoms while green colored atoms are inner <i>fcc</i> atoms. Path which the flying atoms follow are depicted with blue line.	52
5.8	Snapshots of n_{sp1} two phase non-equilibrium simulation at different temperature range	53
5.9	Detailed analysis of solid-to-gas phase transition temperature (T_M) behavior is plotted for different n_{sp} samples and compared with reference bulk. Triangular shaped data-points are T_M value identified from flying atom method. Error bar shows the determined ΔT from the evolution of two-phase non-equilibrium configuration. (a) shows progression of T_M as the diameter (Φ) increases. Black dashed line indicates bulk melting transition temperature $T = 0.56$ at $P = 0.001$. Blue dashed line is for a nearest-neighbor LJ solid model fitted melting temperature $T = 0.5$ at $P = 0$ reported elsewhere (Cowley 1983). In (b) abscissa reports inverse T_M as a function of surface atoms to total atom ratio η in the ordinate. Black and blue squares are denotations of bulk at $P = 0.001$ and $P = 0$ respectively, while red square is the extrapolated T_M of bulk from the linear fit.	54
5.10	Mean squared displacement (msd) of two n_{sp} system, as a function of MD time-steps. Data are shown for T just below T_M and $T = 0.1$ (solid phase) for each nano-system.	55
5.11	Potential energy (E_{Pot}) of (a) n_{sp1} and (b) n_{sp3} , calculated over temperature range of $0.01 - T_M$ at $P = 0$. E_{Pot} is summed over N	56
5.12	Isobaric specific heat (c_p) of n_{sp1} (red), n_{sp2} (green), n_{sp3} (magenta), n_{sp4} (blue) and n_{sp5} (yellow) at $P = 0$, investigated in solid regime. The highest data-point corresponds to the solid-to-gas phase transition (T_M). For comparison, reference bulk data in shown in black. Inset - $c_p(T)$ rescaled over T_M	57
6.1	Snapshots of the initial atomic configurations of (a) n_{sh2} and (b) n_{sh1} . Both samples have free surface in all spatial (x, y, z) directions.	60

- 6.2 Cumulative number density distributions of all n_{sh} samples at $T = 0.15$. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Black and red lines report cumulative density profiles of the n_{sh1} and n_{sh2} respectively. 61
- 6.3 Local density profile of n_{sh1} at $T = 0.25$ rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa, where t is the thickness of the spherical shell. From the deviation of density from average value (green dashed line), five regions have been identified; 1 - internal surface region, 2 - internal interface region, 3 - internal bulk region, 4 - external interface region and 5 - external surface region. Blue (solid) line illustrates the rescaled cumulative distribution trend; only region 3 (internal bulk region) follows the cubic growth (sky blue dashed line). 62
- 6.4 Local density profile of n_{sh2} at $T = 0.25$ rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa, where t is the thickness of the spherical shell. From the deviation of density from average value (green dashed line), three regions have been identified; 1 - internal surface region, 2 - internal bulk region and 3 - external surface region. Blue (solid) line illustrates the rescaled cumulative distribution trend; only region 2 (internal bulk region) follows the cubic growth (sky blue dashed line). 63
- 6.5 Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis of investigates systems. Green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms, blue colored atoms are inner *hcp* atoms and maroon colored atoms are surface atoms with unknown local structure of (a) n_{sh1} at $T = 0.01$, (b) n_{sh1} at $T = 0.25$, (c) n_{sh2} at $T = 0.01$ and (d) n_{sh2} at $T = 0.25$. Different phonon modes can be seen emerging on the surfaces. 64
- 6.6 Trajectories of the flying atoms. Using Ackland-Jones bond-angle method, atoms on the surfaces are marked with maroon color, blue colored atoms are inner *hcp* atoms while green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms. Path which the flying atoms follow are depicted with blue line. 65
- 6.7 Potential energy (E_{Pot}) of (a) n_{sh1} and (b) n_{sh2} , calculated over temperature range of $0.01 - T_M$ at $P = 0$. E_{Pot} is summed over N 65

- 6.8 Isobaric specific heat (c_p) of n_{sh1} (red) and n_{sh2} (green) at $P = 0$, investigated in solid regime. The highest data-point corresponds to the solid-to-gas phase transition (T_M). For comparison, reference bulk data in shown in black. Inset - $c_p(T)$ rescaled over T_M 66

List of Tables

1.1	Specific interface area for bulky materials, nano-materials and foams.	3
3.1	Reduced Lennard-Jones quantities	19
4.1	Studied Nano-slabs. Here Δ is the thickness of the samples, η is the ratio between surface atoms and total number of atoms, N is the total number of atoms.	25
4.2	Average number of surface atoms and inner (<i>fcc</i>) atoms in all n_{sl} systems reported at $T = 0.01$ and $T = 0.2$. Estimated using Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis.	31
4.3	Solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) of all n_{sl} samples, derived from flying atom method.	32
4.4	Scaling law of the specific heat for curvature-free nanoslabs (n_{sl}). Total number of surface atoms are assumed to be constant and the surface area is calculated from the geometry.	40
5.1	Studied Nano-spheres. Here ϕ is the diameter of the samples, N is the total number of atoms in each systems and η is the ratio between geometric surface atoms and total number of atoms.	44
5.2	Average number of surface (<i>unknown</i>) atoms, inner (<i>fcc</i>) atoms and (<i>hcp</i>) in all n_{sp} systems reported at $T = 0.01$ and $T = 0.2$. Estimated using Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis.	51
5.3	Solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) of all n_{sp} samples, derived from flying atom method	51

6.1	Studied Hollow nano-shells. Here ϕ_{out} is the outer diameter of the samples, t is the shell thickness, N is the total number of atoms in each systems and η is the ratio between geometric surface atoms and total number of atoms (in this case the systems have two surface regions - one surface is trapped inside while other one is free.	60
6.2	Average number of surface (<i>unknown</i>) atoms, inner (<i>fcc</i>) atoms and (<i>hcp</i>) in all n_{sh} systems reported at $T = 0.01$ and $T = 0.2$. Estimated using Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis	63
6.3	Solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) of all n_{sh} samples, derived from flying atom method	64

Chapter 1

Introduction

The global energy transformation is finally gaining momentum with renewable energy being established as a "*mainstream source of electricity*" (Smith 2017). Holding a significant share in the global renewable energy production capacity by the end of 2019, Solar power have been projected to be world's largest source of electricity by 2050 (IRENA 2019). Two ways energy can be harvested from the sun, either transforming to electricity - Photovoltaic (PV); or converting to thermal energy - Concentrated solar power (CSP). CSP has precedence over PV as it can be dispatched on demand. Also CSP actively takes over fossil fuel as the "*power block*" of CSP works the same way any conventional power plant (Murphy et al. 2019) .

In CSP plants, concentrating the Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) on the receiver filled with heat transfer/storage fluid, by using arrays of mirrors and lenses, the net heat can be stored in a Thermal energy storage (TES) tank, which enables continuous supply of heat (Duffie & Beckman 2013). There are several mechanisms in which heat can be stored in TES material, as given in Figure.1.1. Being an indispensable part of the CSP industry, TES systems and materials have gained much attention in recent years. With *SunShot Initiative* by the US Department of Energy and *HORIZON-STE* - a Horizon 2020 funded project by European Commission, some effective criteria for a new generation of heat storage fluids were introduced to surpass the unsubsidised cost of fossil fuel-generated electricity (Multidisciplinary University Research Initiative 2012). This helped to thrust the research activities on heat storage fluids with a

common objective to reach the targeted thermal properties, such as lower melting point, increased heat capacity and better thermal stability.

The predominant materials for high temperature applications in TES are the molten salts. To go beyond the thermal constrains of these materials - *nano-structuring expands thermal limits* (Kim et al. 2007) - nano-structuring of bulky material appears to be a optimistic paradigm, and many expectations are placed on it. This approach generates an enormous amount of interface region within the material, which can be characterised by several measurable macroscopic thermodynamic properties. The specific interface area of some given nanomaterials are reported in Table.1.1.

Figure 1.1: Different types of possible thermal storage materials. TES system can be distinguished in three types by the mechanism of storing heat. In sensible heat storage systems, nanofluids, being the predominant material to store heat in a CSP, dominated research in recent years. Sensible-latent heat storage system is also in the forefront of innovation owing to higher energy storage density of such corresponding materials.

As nanomaterials materialized as a "natural laboratory" to probe interface properties as well as to study the impact of it in basic thermodynamics properties such as specific heat ($c_{p,nm}$) and the onset of phase transitions ($T_{M,nm}$); Nanoparticles based

Material	Specific interface area (cm ² /g)
Microporous carbon foam (Ma et al. 2001)	$\approx 2.9 \times 10^7$
Mesoporous carbon foam (Zhou et al. 2017)	$\approx 9.81 \times 10^6$
Macro-mesoporous carbon foam (Karthik et al. 2015, 2017)	$\approx 1.35 - 4.45 \times 10^6$
SiO ₂ in KNO ₃	$\approx 2.86 \times 10^5$
SiO ₂ in [C ₄ mim][BF ₄] (Gao et al. 2015)	$\approx 6.83 \times 10^4$
KNO ₃	4.71×10^0
SiO ₂	2.86×10^0
Au	6.72×10^{-1}

Table 1.1: Specific interface area for bulky materials, nano-materials and foams.

molten salt nano-fluids had been introduced in the last decade as a promising candidate for the next generation of heat storage fluids (Shin & Banerjee 2011). Despite being extensively studied by several groups, experimental behaviour of the specific heat behaviors of these nano-fluids lack conformity with all the phenomenological models proposed so far. Such thermal instability with varying temperature dependence, ranging from increase to decrease, of the specific heats have been extensively reviewed recently (Arthur & Karim 2016, Hentschke 2016, Riazi et al. 2016). A common conclusion can be drawn from all these reviews: all experimental studies lacks the quantitative analysis of the nanoparticle aggregation dynamics of the colloidal suspension and the interface interaction of nanoparticles.

Arising interpretations of experimental knowledge point to a dynamic interface description of nanoparticle with its suspending medium (Bolmatov & Trachenko 2011, Bolmatov et al. 2012, Trachenko & Brazhkin 2016, D’Aguanno et al. 2018). It can be asserted that to date, there are no direct measurements of the reconstruction of surface of the nanoparticle. To identify the physics behind the fluctuation of the specific heat as well as the setup of the phase-transition of nano-particles, this work presents All-Atom Classical Molecular Dynamics simulations of well defined statistical mechanical models with *Lennard Jones potential*. The aim of coherent interface description of thermodynamic and thermostatic properties in terms of collective lattice vibrational modes in solid phases has been achieved in this study. To define design criteria of new nano-materials with larger specific heat, this model, valid in solid regime, is also used to generalise the results to slab-like nanomaterials of different thicknesses, to nanospheres of different diameters, and also to hollow nanospheres (being prototypes

for nano-encapsulation).

Summarizing, this thesis presents the physical mechanism behind the thermal properties of crystalline nanomaterials as a function of shape and size. The cases in study refer three different nano-structures; nano-slabs, nano-spheres and hollow nano-spheres, using important statistical mechanical models which have been explored with classical molecular dynamics techniques.

After this Chapter, in which the basis and direction of this thesis have been discussed by focusing on the present day scenario, a brief literature review will be presented in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 introduces the basic description of statistical mechanics and classical molecular dynamics along with the detailed data analysis methods. In Chapter 4, 5 and 6; the size and temperature controlled thermostatic and thermodynamic properties of three types of nanomaterials are studied: nanoslabs (finite system without curvature), nanospheres (isolated finite system with curved surfaces) and hollow nanospheres (isolated finite system with negative curved surface inside). All the inferences drawn from the results as well as the direction for future research are proposed in Chapter 7. All MD input files and data analysis codes (written in Fortran 90) are included in the Appendix Sections (data files are available upon request from the author).

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Nanofluids for Heat Storage - Present Scenario

Researchers have long been exploiting nanostructures to manipulate properties (especially thermal) of solids and liquids. In nonmetals, crystal vibrations or otherwise known as "phonons" are the dominant heat carriers; owing to their characteristic lengths at nanoscale. Kim et al. (2007) proposed future research direction with major implications on thermal energy storage systems. Since inception (Shin & Banerjee 2011), despite being considered to be the next-gen of storage technology, "nanofluids have been receiving a growing amount of attention in the past decade despite the controversy and inconsistencies that have been reported." (Arthur & Karim 2016). Hentschke (2016) stated by reviewing numerous experimental results, to understand these discrepancies, "A molecular theory explaining ... the specific heat capacity of heat transfer fluids does not yet exist". Further Riazi et al. (2016) also commented that "the fundamental governing mechanisms for the observed changes in this property have not yet been agreed upon". Heat capacity in gases and solids are well understood, but not in liquids; Bolmatov & Trachenko (2011) proposed solid-state approach to the collective phonon modes in liquids, from the anharmonic contribution to heat capacity. With this new description, recent studies by D'Aguzzo et al. (2018) and Engelmann & Hentschke (2019) on nanofluids link the surface and interface phonon

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contributions to the thermostatic properties.

2.2 Thermal Properties of LJ Nanoparticles

The LJ 12-6 potential has an almost unassailable status in classical atomic or molecular simulations. While the analysis of thermal properties (especially the heat capacity) of bulk LJ solid had been carried out by Wette et al. (1971), Cowley (1983), Li & Johnson (1992) years ago, to the author's knowledge, size dependence of such properties in a finite system has not been explored extensively. Known to be existing in either *fcc* or *hcp* structure (Van de Waal 1991), solid LJ finite structure, Polak (2006) studied size dependence structure instabilities. Although the systems under investigations were solid clusters. Pretti et al. (2019) reported free energies of finite-sized LJ crystallites in colloids. While Van Sang et al. (2013), Thi Thuy Huong et al. (2014) have reported some thermodynamic properties (such as specific heat, radial distribution functions) over a wide range of temperature, they only studied system of one size. Frantz (2001) found "magic number" behaviour with LJ clusters of atom, using Monte Carlo methods. Lacks & Shukla (1996) calculated via perturbation theory and molecular dynamics, the contribution to the free energy arising from anharmonicity.

2.3 Phase Transition of LJ Nanoparticles

For crystalline solid, universal description of phase transition has always been obscure. Frenkel (1946) reasoned the microscopic importance of the surface in melting,

"It is well known that under ordinary circumstances an overheating (of a crystal), similar to the over-heating of a liquid, is impossible. This peculiarity is connected with the fact that the melting of a crystal, which is kept at a homogeneous temperature, always begins on its free surface. The role of the latter must, accordingly, consist in lowering the activation energy, which is necessary for the formation of the liquid phase, i.e., of a

All quoted texts are original words from the author(s) of respective citations.

thin liquid layer, down to zero."

For several years a comprehensive understanding of first-order phase transitions, opposed to second-order changes, did not develop much beyond the macroscopic level (Dash 1999). While bulk phase transitions are well understood, it is very difficult to formulate uniform comprehension of finite systems (Löwen 1994). Recent progress addressed this issues with different approaches,

1. *experiment* - scattering analysis with nanometer range resolution and time scale,
2. *computer simulation* - simple model considering inter-atomic interaction, and
3. *theory* - semi-phenomenological or microscopic, with thermodynamic relevance of physical mechanisms.

Indications of surface melting had been found in several molecular lever experiments (Frenken et al. 1986, 1988), theoretical aspects have been studied by computer simulations (Landa et al. 1996) and density functional approach (Ohnesorge et al. 1994). Martin et al. (1994) detected size-dependent phase transition with finite spherical systems, as well as depression of value well below melting temperature of the bulk. Cotterill (1975) found depression in melting point in a very thin close-packed "pseudo-infinite" LJ crystal, approximately 5% lower than bulk (without surface) system. Melting of *fcc* LJ nanoparticles had been investigated by Van Sang et al. (2013), using molecular dynamics simulations at wide temperature range. The authors reported emergence of quasi-liquid layers far below melting point. Much as Wallace (1991) formulated a melting rule based on energy and entropy of solid and liquid phases, Trayanov & Tosatti (1988) developed "a lattice theory of surface melting", by carefully evaluating order parameters and surface free energy. Samsonov et al. (2009) showed size effects during the melting of LJ nanoparticles and "chaotic distribution of atoms" in the surface layer, and also demonstrated liquid-like layer formation initiating at the surface. A very recent work by Fan et al. (2020) examined surface mediated melting in a more realistic settings and observed surface correlation and diffusion of

All quoted texts are original words from the author(s) of respective citations.

atoms inside the bulk layer to mediate melting. A recent review by Gaston (2018) discussed various influences on melting temperatures in cluster-like finite systems.

To conclude, "The story of surface melting is not yet complete. Still to be explored is the evolution of lateral structure. ... Such an evolution can be inferred from some computer simulations ..." (Dash 1999).

Chapter 3

Theory and Conceptual Details

3.1 Classical Molecular Dynamics

"Can we predict the macroscopic properties of many-body systems?" Basic idea of simulation is to input controlled parameters of the system and compute the output data. The connection between input and output establishes a theory.

Newton gave us time evolution of the system. Laplace envisioned with that knowledge future behaviour can be predicted. The concept of phase space developed by Boltzmann leads to the static properties of the system. With the key idea of *motion*, Molecular Dynamics simulation describes how individual atoms in matter change trajectories, velocity and orientations with time. Interpretation of these changes lead to quantitative predictions of structure, properties and dynamics of matter in solid, liquid or gas phases (Haile 1992). With the pioneering studies of the interactions of hard spheres by Alder and Wainwright in 1950s (Alder & Wainwright 1957, 1959), Molecular dynamics was introduced as a simulation technique. MD is indeed a "computer experiment" which enables to investigate different theoretical models. Main advantage of MD is the ability to impart information that are not directly accessible by "real" experiments (Heiser 1984).

Simulated model in MD can be described as a conjugate of inter-molecular interaction and system-environment interaction. The molecular energy can be expressed as a sum of individual pair interactions;

$$U = \sum_{i < j} U(r_{ij}) \quad (3.1)$$

where $U(r_{ij})$ is the known pair potential energy as a function of the spacing, r_{ij} , between molecule i and j . Using Born-Oppenheimer approximation, Newton's 2nd law of motion can be applied on a system of atoms. Molecular interaction energy function U will determine the force. Assuming the coordinates of n th atom of a N -atom system $\zeta_{n,x}$, $\zeta_{n,y}$, $\zeta_{n,z}$ and mass m_n , the equations of motion as follows,

$$m_n \frac{d^2 \zeta_{n,x}}{dt^2} = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial \zeta_{n,x}} \quad m_n \frac{d^2 \zeta_{n,y}}{dt^2} = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial \zeta_{n,y}} \quad m_n \frac{d^2 \zeta_{n,z}}{dt^2} = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial \zeta_{n,z}} \quad (3.2)$$

Employing statistical mechanics description of macrostate, the energy-environment interaction can be linked with statistical distribution of microstate ensembles. The characteristics of boundary conditions where $N \rightarrow \infty$ determines the system properties. With *ergodic hypothesis* stating ensemble average equals to time average, sampling over equiprobable microstate via time evolution gives the system properties (McQuarrie 1976, Haile 1992, Leimkuhler & Matthews 2015). A very generic implementation flowchart of MD code should be executed is shown in Fig. 3.1

3.1.1 Thermodynamics Ensemble Constraints

An ensemble is a collection of equiprobable systems, constructed to be an ideal replica of thermodynamics state of a macroscopic system. Assuming the macrosystem has volume V , N atoms and energy E . If the system is isolated, ensemble with ξ number of microsystem would have ξN atoms, volume of ξV and total energy of $\varepsilon = \xi E$ (Gibbs 1902). Three important thermodynamic ensembles for molecular dynamics simulations are

- **Microcanonical Ensemble or NVE** - In this ensemble, number of atoms

Figure 3.1: A typical flow-chart of MD simulation

(N), volume (V) and energy (E) are kept constant. This is an adiabatic process where no heat exchange occurs in order to stay in equilibrium.

- **Canonical Ensemble or NVT** - A statistical ensemble, where number of atoms (N), volume (V) and temperature (T) are conserved. This refers to a

closed system with a coupling with a heat bath.

- **Isothermal-Isobaric Ensemble or NPT** - In this ensemble, number of atoms (N), pressure (P) and temperature (T) are fixed. In addition to a heat bath, coupling with barostat is also needed. It corresponds most closely to laboratory conditions.

3.1.2 Interatomic Interaction Potentials

Inter-atomic interaction potentials are simplified analytical functions to model the potential energy function as shown in Eq. 3.1 arising from the acting quantum mechanical forces of electrons and nuclei (Brenner 2000). To study continuous collective phenomena having many atoms at atomic scale, there are many varieties of these potentials (Rapaport 2004).

Lennard-Jones potential

Proposed by Sir John Edward Lennard-Jones, this potential describes the potential energy between two non-bonding atoms based on their separation length. The Lennard-Jones model consists of a steep Pauli repulsion term and smoother Van der Waals attractive term (Jones 1924). The potential can be formed by the following equation;

$$V(r) = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^6 \right] \quad (3.3)$$

where V is inter-molecular potential between the atoms. ϵ is the well depth and a measure of how strongly the two particles attract each other. σ is the distance at which the inter-molecular potential between the two particles attract each other is zero i.e. the *Van der Waals* diameter, r is the separation distance between two atoms. In Figure. 3.2, the interaction energy as a function of inter-molecular distance has been depicted. Due to its computational expediency, the Lennard-Jones potential is used extensively in computer simulations. It can accurately model van der Waals interaction in noble gases (McDonald & Singer 1967), several molecular solids (Heinz et al. 2008, Damyanova et al. 2009) as well as few organic materials (Mamedov &

Figure 3.2: The Lennard-Jones 12-6 potential approximates the intermolecular interactions of two atoms due to Pauli repulsion and Van der Waals attraction between non-ionic particles. [Image copied from <https://glossary.periodni.com/glossary.php?en=Lennard-Jones+potential> (Generalic 2018)]

Somuncu 2014). Here LJ potential is used for the investigation of material non-specific general classes of effects. The following Fig. 3.3 is a typical phase diagram of Lennard-Jones system in the temperature-pressure plane.

3.1.3 Integration Algorithms

The potential energy of a system is a function of the atomic coordinates ($3N$) of all the atoms. The equations of motion cannot be solved analytically due to the intricacy of this function. To solve numerically, several numerical algorithms have been implemented to integrate the equations of motion (Schneider et al. 2008).

All the integration algorithms assume the positions, velocities and accelerations

Figure 3.3: Phase diagram of the LJ system. Reprinted from (Travasset 2014), with the permission of AIP Publishing.

can be approximated by a Taylor series expansion:

$$r(t + \delta t) = r(t) + v(t)\delta t + \frac{1}{2}a(t)\delta t^2 + \dots \quad (3.4)$$

$$v(t + \delta t) = v(t) + a(t)\delta t + \frac{1}{2}b(t)\delta t^2 + \dots \quad (3.5)$$

$$r(t + \delta t) = a(t) + b(t)\delta t + \dots \quad (3.6)$$

Where r is the position, v is the velocity (the first derivative with respect to time), a is the acceleration (the second derivative with respect to time).

Verlet Algorithm

To derive the Verlet algorithm one can write equation 3.4 and

$$r(t - \delta t) = r(t) - v(t)\delta t + \frac{1}{2}a(t)\delta t^2 + \dots \quad (3.7)$$

Summing these two equations, one obtains,

$$r(t + \delta t) = 2r(t) - r(t - \delta t) + a(t)\delta t^2 \quad (3.8)$$

The Verlet algorithm uses positions and accelerations at time t and the positions from time $t - \delta t$ to calculate new positions at time $t + \delta t$ (Verlet 1967).

The Leap-frog algorithm

In this algorithm, the velocities are first calculated at time $t + 1/2\delta t$; these are used to calculate the positions, r , at time $t + \delta t$. In this way, the velocities *leap* over the positions, then the positions *leap* over the velocities (Hockney & Eastwood 1988).

$$r(t + \delta t) = r(t) + v(t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t)\delta t \quad (3.9)$$

$$v(t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t) = v(t - \frac{1}{2}\delta t) + a(t)\delta t \quad (3.10)$$

The velocities at time t can be approximated by the relationship:

$$v(t) = \frac{1}{2} \left[v\left(t - \frac{1}{2}\delta t\right) + v\left(t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t\right) \right] \quad (3.11)$$

The Velocity Verlet algorithm

This algorithm yields positions, velocities and accelerations at time t . There is no compromise on precision (Swope et al. 1982).

$$r(t + \delta t) = r(t) + v(t)\delta t + \frac{1}{2}a(t)\delta t^2 \quad (3.12)$$

$$v(t + \delta t) = v(t) + \frac{1}{2}[a(t) + a(t + \delta t)]\delta t \quad (3.13)$$

3.2 Physical Quantities of Interest from MD Simulation

As per the *ergodic hypothesis*, if the system is allowed to evolve, it will pass through all possible microscopic states eventually. By generating enough MD trajectories, we can extract relevant, structural, dynamic as well as thermodynamic properties.

3.2.1 Energy

Energy has two terms, kinetic and potential. Potential energy has contribution from interaction between particles as well as external potential. It could be expressed as follows,

$$E_{Pot} = V_{int}(\vec{r}_1, \dots, \vec{r}_N) + \sum_{i=1}^N U_{ext}^i(\vec{r}_i) \quad (3.14)$$

The Kinetic energy can be calculated from the momenta p_i ,

$$E_{Kin} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{m_i}{2} \vec{v}_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{p_i^2}{2m_i} \quad (3.15)$$

Total energy of the system is,

$$\langle E \rangle = \langle E_{Kin} \rangle + \langle E_{Pot} \rangle \quad (3.16)$$

3.2.2 Temperature

The instantaneous temperature of a system of N particles of masses m_i and momentum p_i is,

$$T = \frac{1}{3Nk_B} \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|p_i|^2}{m_i} \right\rangle \quad (3.17)$$

This instantaneous temperature fluctuates around the true thermodynamic temperature along with the E_{Kin} of the system. Therefore to get an accurate estimate, it should be time-averaged (Allen & Tildesley 2017).

3.2.3 Pressure

Pressure is a second order tensor. Among the various ways to calculate the pressure, here it is measured by the formula,

$$P = \frac{Nk_B T}{V} + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N r_i \cdot f_i}{dV} \quad (3.18)$$

where r_i and f_i are the coordinates and force vector of i atom (Schneider et al. 2008).

3.2.4 Pair Correlation Function

The pair (or radial) correlation function $g(r)$ defines the thermodynamic properties of the system. This gives the probability of finding the center of an atom from the center of another atom at a given distance. For crystalline solids, $g(r)$ exhibits major peaks in a sequence at positions of shell around an atom (McQuarrie 1976). It is defined as,

$$g(r) = \frac{V}{N^2} \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N \delta(r - r_{ij}) \right\rangle \quad (3.19)$$

This holds as one of the most important physical quantity in many-body physics. The 2nd order parameter $g^2(r_1, r_2)$ is directly related to the structure factor of the system. Experimentally it is calculated from neutron/X-ray diffraction. The average of any physical quantity that is dependent on pair potential $u(r)$ can be expressed as an integral over $g(r)$. For a three-dimensional system, E_{Pot} of the system can be calculated as,

$$E_{Pot} = \frac{N}{2} 4\pi\rho \int_0^\infty r^2 u(r) g(r) dr \quad (3.20)$$

where ρ is the number density and N is the total number of atoms.. Developing the *virial equation* calculates the pressure equation of states.

3.2.5 Specific Heat

This is usually defined by how much heat required per unit mass to increase the temperature by one degree. In statistical mechanics, the specific heat is calculated

by the energy fluctuation,

$$\langle \delta E^2 \rangle_{NVT} = k_B T^2 C_V \quad (3.21)$$

where C_V is constant-volume specific heat and $\langle \delta E^2 \rangle_{NVT} = \langle E^2 \rangle - \langle E \rangle^2$. For MD, this method can produce statistical errors (Rapaport 2004). Instead, direct relation as shown below is favoured on account of its accuracy.

$$c_v = \left(\frac{\partial \langle E(T) \rangle_{NVT}}{\partial T} \right) \quad \text{or} \quad c_p = \left(\frac{\partial \langle H(T) \rangle_{NPT}}{\partial T} \right) \quad (3.22)$$

where $\partial \langle E(T) \rangle_{NVT}$ and $\partial \langle H(T) \rangle_{NPT}$ are solved analytically with best fitting polynomial.

3.2.6 Mean Squared Displacement

Mean Squared Displacement (*msd*) is the ensemble average of the square of the spatial deviation of the atoms from a reference (equilibrium) position. *msd* at a time duration t can be expressed as follows,

$$msd \equiv \langle |x(t) - x_0|^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x^{(i)}(t) - x^{(i)}(0)|^2 \quad (3.23)$$

where $x^{(i)}(0)$ is the equilibrium position of i -th particle (Heiser 1984). Self-diffusion coefficient can be related to the *msd* of an atom as a function of time by Einstein relation, as the slope of *msd*(t) is proportional to D , the diffusion coefficient.

3.2.7 Density Profile

A density profile is defined as the density in a given volume ΔV located at a distance r from a given reference point. By using the particle positions generated in a MD simulation, the number density profile arising from spherical shell volumes between r and $r + \delta r$ can be expressed as,

$$\rho_N(r) = \frac{\langle N(r) \rangle}{\Delta V(r)} = \frac{\langle N(r) \rangle}{\frac{4}{3}\pi[(r + \delta r)^3 - r^3]} \quad (3.24)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ is the standard MD configurational average and $N(r)$ is the number of atoms in the shell volume $\Delta V(r)$.

3.3 Reduced Units

When simulating LJ systems which has only one type of molecule, it is convenient to set mass of the atom, $m_i = 1$, as a fundamental unit. This causes the momenta p_i and velocities v_i to be identical. so do the acceleration a_i and forces f_i . With the Boltzmann constant, $k_B = 1$, extending this approach further, in Eq. 3.3 system can be completely specified by $\sigma = 1$ and $\epsilon = 1$; then fundamental units of length, energy can also be described. This allows computing values to be closer to unity and can be used to scale results for various physical properties (Allen & Tildesley 2017). The formulas relating the reduced or unit-less quantity (with an asterisk) to the same quantity with units is given in the Table. 3.1. From now on, all quantities will be

Property	Reduced form
Length (σ)	where $r^* = \frac{r}{\sigma}$
Time (τ)	where $\tau^* = \tau \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{m\sigma^2}}$
Energy (ϵ)	where $E^* = \frac{E}{\epsilon}$
Temperature (reduced LJ temperature)	where $T^* = \frac{k_B T}{\epsilon}$
Pressure (reduced LJ pressure)	where $P^* = \frac{P\sigma^3}{\epsilon}$
Density (mass/volume)	where $\rho^* = \rho\sigma^3$

Table 3.1: Reduced Lennard-Jones quantities

specified in terms of reduced units and all extensive quantities will be normalized by the number of atoms.

3.4 Data Analysis Methods

Detailed information about the structures of all the samples were obtained from three criteria, as follows,

1. Local density profile,
2. Cumulative density profile,

3. Ackland-Jones bond-angle method

The formulation of density profile has already been discussed in subsection 3.2.7. The corresponding mass density profile is given by $\rho(r) = \rho_N(r)w_m/A_N$ with w_m the molar weight and A_N the Avogadro number. Instead, the cumulative number density profile, $\rho_{N,C}(r)$, which gives the total number of particles contained in the sphere of radius r , is simply the sum of $\rho_N(r)$ over the considered number of shells between $(0, r)$. In the spherical shell case, and for homogeneous bulk systems, $\rho_{N,C}(r)$ must scale as r^3 . In the cases in which the volumes are slabs between a Cartesian coordinate x and $x + \delta x$, and the bulk systems are still homogeneous, $\rho_{N,C}(x)$ must scale linearly with x . For finite spherical particles and slabs of finite thickness, the deviation of $\rho_{N,C}$ from the previous scaling laws, and prior to the falling to zero of its value, will indicate the appearance of surface regions with a structure different from the bulk structure.

To distinguish the appearance of surface layers for the crystalline finite systems, local crystal coordination analysis were performed based on Ackland-Jones bond-angle method (Ackland & Jones 2006). For crystalline systems, this technique can identify *fcc*, *bcc*, *hcp* and *ico* structures. This allows to identify and tag the atoms belonging to the surface region, interface region or inner bulk region.

To investigate the solid-to-gas phase transition, three different techniques have been considered,

- the flying atom method,
- the evolution of a two phase non-equilibrium configuration, and
- the diffusion of surface atoms

In the *flying atom method*, during a slow-heating simulation, the temperature at which an atom is leaving the nanomaterial surface is recorded. This is achieved by automatically stopping the simulation when the "flying atom" hits the simulation box. Advantage of this method is the ability to inspect visually from the MD trajectory movies. For further validation in the *evolution of a two phase non-equilibrium configuration*, the simulation box is filled with solid phase structure close to the transition

point (as recorded from previous method) and a random distribution of atoms (gas phase). Then the simulated temperature is increased or decreased in order to allow the system to become fully equilibrated, either at solid phase or at gas phase. The process is continued till when $\Delta T = T_g - T_s = 0.02$. By evaluating the *msd* of different regions as coming from the structural analysis, lattice vibrations of the atoms around their equilibrium position were evaluate, along with their diffusion coefficients as described in subsection 3.2.6. Further for bulk system, transition temperature was identified from the slope of potential energy.

The specific heat in a T -range $[T_1, T_2]$ is evaluated by starting from absolute energy-minimized configuration at, say T_1 , (see Fig. 4.2). Then simulations are performed when the final temperature T_2 is reached after a "quite large" number of simulation steps. The results (E_{Pot} or H) are then plotted against T -abscissa with values separated by T -intervals $\Delta T = (T_2 - T_1)/n$ steps. The availability of large number of values for the function to be derived, allows the choice of the best fitting polynomial (with lowest residual) of the function. This "quasi-continuous" method allows the reduction of computational resources of more than one order of magnitudes with respect to methods in which few well equilibrated states are generated in the chosen T -range. As it can be seen from Fig. 3.4, the well equilibrated states coincides with the states generated by the quasi-continuous method. This proves the higher reliability of this method when T -derivatives must be performed. For the nano-slabs, the specific heat is evaluated by,

$$c_{p,ns} = \left(\frac{\partial \langle E_{Pot} \rangle_{NPT}}{\partial T} \right)_{N,P=0} + \frac{3}{2} k_B \quad (3.25)$$

Instead, the following relation is used for the nano-spheres and hollow nano-shells:

$$c_{p,ns} = \left(\frac{\partial \langle E_{Pot} \rangle_{NVT}}{\partial T} \right)_{N,V} + \frac{3}{2} k_B \quad (3.26)$$

Finally, the bulk sample specific heat is calculated with:

$$c_p = \left(\frac{\partial \langle H \rangle_{NPT}}{\partial T} \right)_{N,P} \quad (3.27)$$

where the $\langle E_{Pot}(T) \rangle$ and $\langle H \rangle_{NPT}$ simultaneously, are replaced by the best fitting polynomial and the derivatives are performed analytically. Owing to the largely available data-sets at an extensive range of temperatures in this work, all measured $c_p(T)$ are fitted with quartic functions: $f(x) = a + bx + cx^2 + dx^3 + ex^4$. Using this kind of polynomial for specific heat is a prevailing method in the literature (Wu et al. 2001) and had been benchmarked by McBride et al. (1993).

Figure 3.4: Potential energy behaviour of a nanosystem as a function of temperature. Cyan Square (Empty Square) symbols correspond to step-by-step heating procedure. Solid black line corresponds to the quasi-continuous method. And Orange (Dashed) line is the quartic fit of the quasi-continuous method.

3.5 Tools and Implementation

Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator, or LAMMPS was used to perform the simulation (*LAMMPS website* n.d.). It is a classical molecular dynamics code developed under Cooperative Research and Development Agreement in USA, led by Steve Plimpton at Sandia National Laboratories (Plimpton 1995). LAMMPS uses standard Velocity-Verlet time integrator for simulations. It can run on single processors as well as in message-passing parallel domain. LAMMPS can be used to construct atoms at the atomic scale. Having wide varieties of potential models for materials, LAMMPS can be very inclusive.

For general visualization and post-processing of the output of MD simulation, VMD - "a molecular graphics program", developed by the Theoretical and Computational Biophysics Group at the Beckman Institute for Advanced Science and Technology of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign (Humphrey et al. 1996) and OVITO, "a scientific data visualization and analysis software", developed by Alexander Stukowski at Darmstadt University of Technology, Germany (Stukowski 2010) were used.

All simulations have been performed on a Cray XC30 supercomputer managed by ARCHER, the UK's National Supercomputing Service. It is capable of performing calculations that demand large parallel processing capacity. This work used the ARCHER UK National Supercomputing Service (<http://www.archer.ac.uk>).

Chapter 4

Case Study 1 - Nano-Slab

4.1 Simulation Details

To study free surface in the absence of curvature, 5 samples of Nano-Slabs (n_{sl}) were prepared. The atoms of all n_{sl} have been arranged in face-centered cubic structures. The primitive lattice vectors are

$$\vec{a}_1 = a \times \left[\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 0 \right] \quad \vec{a}_2 = a \times \left[\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2} \right] \quad \vec{a}_3 = a \times \left[0, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right]$$

where lattice distance $a = 1.679$. The structural details of all 5 samples are tabulated in Table. 4.1. The initial configuration, with a reduced density of $\rho = 0.8442$, have been generated by filling the defined geometric regions of spaces with atoms. Snapshots of the initial atomic configurations of all n_{sl} samples are shown in the Fig. 4.1. With constant surface area of 10×10 unit cells, the thickness of the n_{sl} were increased by fixing 2, 4, 7, 11 and 14 unit cells in one spatial directions, consecutively.

	Δ	η	N	Index
	3.358	0.40	1000	n_{sl1}
	6.716	0.22	1800	n_{sl2}
Nano-Slab (n_{sl})	11.753	0.13	3000	n_{sl3}
	18.469	0.08	4600	n_{sl4}
	23.506	0.06	5800	n_{sl5}

Table 4.1: Studied Nano-slabs. Here Δ is the thickness of the samples, η is the ratio between surface atoms and total number of atoms, N is the total number of atoms.

Figure 4.1: Snapshots of the initial atomic positions of (a) n_{SI1} , (b) n_{SI2} , (c) n_{SI3} , (d) n_{SI4} and (e) n_{SI5} respectively. All samples have free surface in the x direction.

The initial configurations were then equilibrated and underwent thermal cycling as shown in the Fig. 4.2 with a slowing heating and cooling rate ($\approx 3.0 \times 10^{-7}$ deg per MD steps). Slowly heating the system allows the superfacies to restructure by reducing the interfacial energy at pre-melted configuration (Alarifi et al. 2013), which later followed by equilibration and slow-cooling, goes spontaneously to the natural surface configuration. Further, a bulk configuration with 1372 atoms arranged in *fcc* with a dimension of $7 \times 7 \times 7$ unit-cell were also prepared as reference. With the inter-atomic interaction defined by the Eq. 3.3, the interaction potential was truncated at distance $r_c = 2.8$ with a shift to 0.0. To conserve the free surface, non-periodic boundary condition in one spatial direction (perpendicular to the free surface) and full periodic boundary conditions in other two directions were implemented. Full periodic boundary conditions in all directions were employed for the bulk system. The equations of motion were integrated in isothermal-isobaric (NPT) ensemble with a timestep size of 0.005. Following the phase diagram of LJ bulk in Fig. 3.3, from $T = 0.01$, the reference bulk system was heated till $T = 0.7$ at $P = 0.001$ at a fixed rate of 1.338×10^{-7} deg per MD steps. All thermal and structural calculations of n_{SI} were performed by using the highlighted configuration in Fig. 4.2 over a temperature range of $T = 0.01$ to $T = 0.4$ and $P = 0$. with Nosé-Hoover style thermostatting and barostatting (Hoover 1985). With a heating rate of 1.3×10^{-7} deg per MD steps, the temperature and the pressure were relaxed every 100 and 1000 simulations steps synchronously. All inputs are included in the appendix section 7.1.1, 7.1.4 and 7.1.7.

Figure 4.2: Scheme for preparing initial configuration. Highlighted part represents the final configuration used for obtaining production part of the simulation

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Structural Analysis

Structural details such as density profile and particle distribution are interesting because we can characterize various thermodynamic phases as well as the surface behaviours. The results of distribution of atoms are shown with varying thickness are presented in Fig. 4.3. All systems expand when heated and it is clearly indicated in the plot. At low temperature ($T = 0.01$), all systems are in similar thermodynamic

states; While at $T = 0.2$ they are unlike. This is reflected in the expansion behavior as the smaller system expands more comparing a bigger system. Density trends of

Figure 4.3: Cumulative density profile of all n_{sl} samples at $T = 0.01$ (Solid line), $T = 0.15$ (Dashed line) and $T = 0.2$ (Dash-dotted line). Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\Delta/2$ in the abscissa. Black, red, blue, green and orange lines reports of the n_{sl1} , n_{sl2} , n_{sl3} , n_{sl4} and n_{sl5} respectively.

all system are reported in Fig. 4.4. While the bulk density is recorded from simulation, the density of n_{sl} cannot be accessed directly, as the thickness is independent of the simulation box size in the direction of free surface. Instead from the cumulative size distributions reported in Fig. 4.3, individual thicknesses were extracted at three temperature range and n_{sl} densities were evaluated. This way the true density of the system is underestimated. It can be seen that the calculated solid phase density shows a strongly non-linear behaviour for smaller size systems; especially n_{sl1} , n_{sl2} and n_{sl3} , whilst n_{sl4} and n_{sl5} have more bulk-like linear trend. This indicates that with the increase of bulk layers (thickness), systems behave similar to bulk state. Although non-linearity of $\rho(T)$ is similar to other smaller systems, n_{sl2} have much higher density values at lower T and it coincides with bulk density at $T = 0.2$. This could be presumably due to the critical surface correlation length of this potential, which has been studied extensively elsewhere (Brovchenko et al. 2005, Wierschem & Manousakis 2011).

Figure 4.4: Density of the investigated n_{SI} systems as a function of temperature. Red, magenta, blue, yellow and green points are the density of n_{SI1} , n_{SI2} , n_{SI3} , n_{SI14} and n_{SI15} consecutively.

For understanding the outermost layers and their evolution with simulation accurately, snapshots of Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis results are shown in Fig. 4.5 while the numerical results are tabulated in Table. 4.2. Although the studied n_{SI} have equal number of surface atoms at low temperature, it can be seen that at higher temperature few atoms from the inner layers move to the surface. For smaller size system, n_{SI1} , many atoms migrates due to higher degree of freedom. Applying Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis in conjunction with the deviation of linear trend of cumulative density profile explicitly defines the surface region. By reading the results of local density profiles revealed in Fig. 4.6a, different considerations can be added. From the peaks, two regions can be distinguished as,

1. *Bulk region* - where the density oscillates around the average bulk density (the slope of density will be zero), and
2. *Surface region* - where the majority of outermost atoms oscillate below average

Figure 4.5: Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis of investigated systems. Green colored atoms are inner fcc atoms, maroon colored atoms are surface atoms with unknown local structure of (a) n_{SI1} at $T = 0.01$, (b) n_{SI1} at $T = 0.2$, (c) n_{SI2} at $T = 0.01$, (d) n_{SI2} at $T = 0.2$, (e) n_{SI3} at $T = 0.01$, (f) n_{SI3} at $T = 0.2$, (g) n_{SI4} at $T = 0.01$, (h) n_{SI4} at $T = 0.2$, (i) n_{SI5} at $T = 0.01$, and (j) n_{SI5} at $T = 0.2$ consecutively. Different phonon modes can be seen emerging on the surface

		$T = 0.01$	$T = 0.2$
n_{Sl1}	N_s	400	417
	N_{in}	600	583
n_{Sl2}	N_s	400	410
	N_{in}	1400	1388
n_{Sl3}	N_s	400	410
	N_{in}	2600	2590
n_{Sl4}	N_s	400	404
	N_{in}	4200	4196
n_{Sl5}	N_s	400	405
	N_{in}	5400	5395

Table 4.2: Average number of surface atoms and inner (*fcc*) atoms in all n_{Sl} systems reported at $T = 0.01$ and $T = 0.2$. Estimated using Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis.

bulk density and decreases steeply to zero.

Above-mentioned notions confirm the absence of bulk layers in case of n_{Sl1} , as evident from Fig. 4.6b, density of all layers oscillates below average bulk density. Also this is observed from Fig. 4.6, at lower temperature ($T = 0.01$) in both samples the atoms are packed in the layers with constant density in each layer and virtually no atoms in between these parallel layers. With increasing temperature ($T = 0.25$) the effective width of layers broaden due to enhanced atomic vibrations.

4.2.2 Phase Transition Analysis

Using the "flying atom" method, starting point of solid-to-gas phase transition has been located for studied n_{Sl} . Snapshots of simulations when one atom leaves the surface are displayed in Fig. 4.7 and the temperatures (T_M) of all samples are listed in Table. 4.3. In preceding sections of results, additional self-consistency checks using different specifications provides a clearer viewpoint. Here to indicate for n_{Sl5} , few maroon atoms ("unknown" structure by Ackland-Jones bond-angle method) are also seen in the inner layers. This is due to the movement of those atoms near periodic boundary.

Further, the evolution of a two phase non-equilibrium configuration were per-

Figure 4.6: Local density profiles of (a) n_{SL5} and (b) n_{SL1} , rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\Delta}{2}$ in the abscissa. Black (dashed) line illustrates the trend at $T = 0.01$ and green (solid) line describes the trend at $T = 0.25$. In the case of n_{SL5} , from the deviation of density from average value, two regions have been identified: Bulk region (yellow), and Surface region (red). Although this consideration is invalid for n_{SL1} - as no bulk layer was present.

<i>Index</i>	T_M
n_{SL1}	0.35
n_{SL2}	0.36
n_{SL3}	0.36
n_{SL4}	0.37
n_{SL5}	0.37

Table 4.3: Solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) of all n_{SL} samples, derived from flying atom method.

formed on n_{SL1} to further elaborate the transition behavior. Initial solid-gas atomic configurations (refer to Fig. 4.8a) are generated by a transient thermal shock to the system, which allows the crystal seed at the core to stay intact when majority of surface atoms are sublimated. By allowing the simulation to equilibrate, as portrayed in

Figure 4.7: Trajectories of the flying atoms for (a) n_{SL1} , (b) n_{SL2} , (c) n_{SL3} , (d) n_{SL4} and (e) n_{SL5} individually. Using Ackland-Jones bond-angle method, atoms on the surfaces are marked with maroon color while green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms. Path which the flying atoms follow are depicted with blue line.

Fig. 4.8b, at $T = 0.35$, the system retains its solid phase. Although, at $T = 0.38$, the system becomes gas as evident in Fig. 4.8c. To reach the gas phase, the simulation has to evolve for a sufficient period of time. It should be noted that $\Delta T = T_g - T_s$, or in this case $\equiv 0.38 - 0.35 = 0.03$ is not intrinsic. It depends on the number of simulations one wants to do; i.e. the numerical limits of ΔT were not explored. Through demonstration of phase transition behavior is manifested in Fig. 4.9. In MD simulations, bulk system is an artificial system having no surface ($\eta = 0$). To draw inference, analysis of T_M trend shows strong depression of T_M for finite systems. Although it grows with thickness, the inverse T_M in Fig. 4.9 inset shows linear trend. Extrapolating this we can safely conclude it will never reach true bulk (MD) T_M values when $\eta \approx 0$ of a finite system.

To check reliability of previously discussed results of phase transition, evolution of the resultant Cartesian component of the mean squared displacement (msd) are investigated for two nano-systems, n_{SL1} and n_{SL5} . Displayed in Fig. 4.10, at $T \rightarrow T_M$,

Figure 4.8: Snapshots of n_{SL1} two phase non-equilibrium simulation at different temperature range

surface layers show typical liquid-like tendency whilst inner-bulk layers stay solid-like (zero slope). Both surface and inner layers remain solid at $T = 0.25$. With liquid-like layer formation on the surface near T_M , these findings are consistent with previous studies (Frenken & Veen 1985, Hakkinen & Landman 1993, Landa et al. 1996), and established theories (Hanszen 1960, Trayanov & Tosatti 1988, Ohnesorge et al. 1994) of surface-driven phase transition.

In search for an universal empirical criteria of melting/phase-transition, a quantitative model developed by Frederick Lindemann (Lindemann 1910) has been accepted as to interpret melting. Despite its widespread use, this criterion has failed in many instances (Meijer & Frenkel 1991, Chakravarty et al. 2007, SARKAR et al. 2017, Fan et al. 2020). Instead, this thesis formulates a Lindemann-like empirical criteria, based on the amplitude of surface phonon modes, to predict the inception of melting for finite systems. While the amplitude of vibration can be seen in Fig. 4.11, the statistics is performed extensively over all (200) atoms in each layer with 5000 static configurations. This framework minimizes configurational errors generated due to thermal fluctuations. In both Fig. 4.11a and Fig. 4.11c, surface and bulk atoms have

Figure 4.9: Detailed analysis of solid-to-gas phase transition temperature (T_M) behavior is plotted for different n_{Sl} samples and compared with reference bulk. Triangular shaped data-points are T_M value identified from flying atom method. Error bar shows the determined ΔT from the evolution of two-phase non-equilibrium configuration. (a) shows progression of T_M as the slab thickness (Δ) increases. Black dashed line indicates Bulk melting transition temperature $T = 0.56$ at $P = 0.001$. Blue dashed line is for a nearest-neighbor LJ solid model fitted melting temperature $T = 0.5$ at $P = 0$ reported elsewhere (Cowley 1983). In (b) abscissa reports inverse T_M as a function of surface atoms to total atom ratio η in the ordinate. Black and blue squares are denotations of bulk at $P = 0.001$ and $P = 0$ respectively, while red square is the extrapolated T_M of bulk from the linear fit

normal distribution. The width of distribution, $\Delta x_{surface}(n_{Sl})$ is numerically identical contrary to $\Delta x_{bulk}(n_{Sl})$. Further close to phase-transition, as seen from Fig. 4.11b and Fig. 4.11d, asymmetry arises to the probability distribution in presence of surface phonons. The skewness value will deviate (positive or negative) away from the free surface directions. However, $\Delta x_{surface}(n_{Sl})$ remains equivalent and size-independent. According to 4.3, average lattice distance, $\langle a \rangle \approx 1.08$. Let us assume $\Delta x_{surface}(T)$ increases linearly. From the statistics in Fig. 4.11b and Fig. 4.11d, $\Delta x_{surface}$ can be expressed as quantity of $\langle a \rangle$ as $\Delta x_{surface} \approx 150\%$ of $\langle a \rangle$. Now, width of distribution

(a) Total squared displacement of n_{S11} at the surface layer. Behaviour of the bulk layer is shown in inset. At $T = 0.34$, surface behaves "liquid-like" albeit bulk layer is "solid-like".

(b) Total squared displacement of n_{S15} at the surface layer. Behaviour of the bulk layer is shown in inset. At $T = 0.36$, surface behaves "liquid-like" albeit bulk layer is "solid-like".

Figure 4.10: Mean squared displacement (msd) of smallest and largest n_{SI} system, as a function of MD time-steps. Data are shown for T just below T_M and $T = 0.25$ (solid phase) for each nano-system.

(a) For n_{SL1} ; continuum vibration amplitudes of surface and bulk (inset) atoms at $T = 0.05$.

(b) For n_{SL1} ; continuum vibration amplitudes of surface and bulk (inset) atoms at $T = 0.34$.

(c) For n_{SL5} ; continuum vibration amplitudes of surface and bulk (inset) atoms at $T = 0.05$.

(d) For n_{SL5} ; continuum vibration amplitudes of surface and bulk (inset) atoms at $T = 0.36$.

Figure 4.11: Normal distribution of probability density function attributed to the surface (soft) phonons and bulk (hard) phonons. Red dashed lines are the average lattice positions at corresponding T , calculated from the x -Cartesian component of the msd.

away from surface ($\Delta_{surface}$) exactly attributes when atom ejects from the surface. Based on this knowledge, it is predicted that phase-transition (through ejection of surface atom) occur when

$$\Delta_{Surface} \geq 1.18 \times \langle a \rangle \quad (4.1)$$

Since this estimation in previous Eq. 4.1 is based on fundamental description of matter, a rather genericness of the formulation can be asserted.

Figure 4.12: Potential energy (E_{Pot}) of (a) n_{Sl1} and (b) n_{Sl5} , calculated over temperature range of $0.01 - T_M$ at $P = 0$. E_{Pot} is summed over N .

4.2.3 Specific Heat Analysis

To characterize specific heat (c_p), preliminary analysis of $E_{Pot}(T)$ is presented in Fig. 4.12 focusing only on solid phase. All E_{Pot} grows non-linearly with 4-th order fitting polynomial. Now to understand the temperature and size dependence of specific heat (c_p), the values are shown in Fig. 4.13. The values are obtained from derivatives of MD E_{Pot} plots in Fig. 4.12 using Eq. 3.25. Smallest system n_{Sl1} has the highest increase of c_p near transition followed by n_{Sl2} . While n_{Sl3} , n_{Sl4} and n_{Sl5} exhibit analogous growth, they are indistinguishable from each-other. By rescaling $c_p(T)$ over T_M , all systems can be represented in invariable thermodynamic states. From the plot, it is evident that $c_p(T/T_M)$ starts deviating from linear trend at $0.6T_M$. This is presumably linked to the initiation of surface premelting which happens around 20 – 30% below true T_M . At very low T ($\approx 0.01 - 0.05$), the curves of c_p are biased by the fitting procedure; performing piece-wise differentiation could give better values.

Figure 4.13: Isobaric specific heat (c_p) of n_{Sl1} (red), n_{Sl2} (green), n_{Sl3} (magenta), n_{Sl4} (blue) and n_{Sl5} (yellow) at $P = 0$, investigated in solid regime. The highest data-point corresponds to the solid-to-gas phase transition (T_M). For comparison, reference bulk data in shown in black. Inset - $c_p(T)$ rescaled over T_M .

From the density profiles, the system has already demonstrated to be made by two regions, an inner (bulk) region and an outer (surface) region. By knowing total number of atoms N_t , atoms in the outer region will be given by $N_{out} = N_t - N_{in}$. Correspondingly, in ideal case the specific heat of n_{Sl} is given by,

$$c_{p,nsI} \left(\Delta, \frac{T}{T_M} \right) = x_{in} c_{p,in} \left(\Delta, \frac{T}{T_M} \right) + x_{out} c_{p,out} \left(\Delta, \frac{T}{T_M} \right) \quad (4.2)$$

in which $x_i = N_i / (N_{in} + N_{out})$. If it is assumed that $c_{p,in} \left(\Delta, \frac{T}{T_M} \right) = c_{p,bulk} \left(\frac{T}{T_M} \right)$. $c_{p,nsI}$ and $c_{p,bulk}$ are accessible from the MD simulation. So the previous Eq. 4.2 gives the estimate of the determination of $c_{p,out} \left(\Delta, \frac{T}{T_M} \right)$;

$$c_{p,out} \left(\Delta, \frac{T}{T_M} \right) = \frac{1}{x_{out}} \left[c_{p,nsI} \left(\Delta, \frac{T}{T_M} \right) - x_{in} c_{p,bulk} \left(\frac{T}{T_M} \right) \right] \quad (4.3)$$

$\frac{T}{T_M}$	<i>Index</i>	$c_{p,bulk}$ [Nk_B]	$c_{p,nsl}$ [Nk_B]	x_{out}	$c_{p,out}$ [Nk_B]	C^* [$Nk_B\sigma^{-2}$]
1.0	n_{sl1}	3.4901	3.9753	0.4	4.2922	0.0174
	n_{sl2}		3.7040	0.222	3.7623	0.0152
	n_{sl3}		3.6288	0.133	3.6486	0.0148
	n_{sl4}		3.619	0.086	3.6303	0.0147
	n_{sl5}		3.6089	0.069	3.6169	0.0147
0.9	n_{sl1}	3.4104	3.7376	0.4	3.9560	0.0160
	n_{sl2}		3.5626	0.222	3.6062	0.0146
	n_{sl3}		3.4846	0.133	3.4960	0.0142
	n_{sl4}		3.474	0.086	3.4801	0.0141
	n_{sl5}		3.467	0.069	3.4712	0.0141

Table 4.4: Scaling law of the specific heat for curvature-free nanoslabs (n_{sl}). Total number of surface atoms are assumed to be constant and the surface area is calculated from the geometry.

From the MD simulation results, all variables of Eq. 4.3 are tabulated in Table. 4.4 for planar n_{sl} nano-particles with different thickness Δ , where C^* is the specific heat per unit of n_{sl} surface. Now quantifying the effect of $c_{p,nsl}$ deviation in from $c_{p,bulk}$. it is evident that surface layer produces the high contribution albeit small in larger systems owing to smaller fraction. As can be seen in the Table. 4.4, when surface correlation goes to zero that is both surfaces are far from each other, the C^* remains constant. With this factor, a comprehensive scaling law for the specific heat of nanoparticles with planar surfaces can be constructed with as an invariance added to the specific heat of bulk,

$$c_{p,nsl} = x_{in}c_{p,bulk} + x_{out}AC^* \quad (4.4)$$

where A is the surface area of the finite system. This relation is valid only for systems with planar geometrical surface. Summarizing,

Scaling law: For slab thickness larger than 4 unit cells, and for the same rescaled temperature T/T_M , the specific heat per unit of slab surface area is a constant; and the heat capacity scales linearly.

4.3 Discussion

In this chapter, thermostatic properties of LJ-nanoslabs have been investigated, with conjectural relevance to the surface. Structural evolution upon heating is studied by analysing several independent criteria such as - local and cumulative density profile, Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis. These provided an overview of the allocation of atoms in various layers as well as the surface and bulk layer separations.

Next, calculating solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) with flying-atom method gives an idea of premelting and initiation of transition through surface. Additionally, information regarding the progression of phase transition between layers were obtained from two-phase non-equilibrium simulation incorporated with atomic mean-square displacements with liquid-like layer formed at the surface. While T_M of flat finite system is directly proportional to the size (thickness), it diverges from T_M value in absence of surface. Further, accurate theoretical estimation based on the amplitudes of "soft" surface phonons predicted the starting of phase-transition in a curvature-free open-surface system.

Specific heat, c_p of studied systems found to be increasing with temperature and strongly size-dependent; that is smaller system will have higher enhancements in c_p comparing bulk counterpart. Thermodynamically, the specific heat is very nicely linked to the extensive physical quantities, but is introduced and defined as the derivative of the E_{Pot} . The role of E_{Pot} , better determined from MD, influences the shape of the specific heat function on physical (specific heat has to strongly increase at low T , almost flatten at intermediate T , sharp increase close to T_M) and numerical (residuals of the fits) grounds. Finally, an universal scaling law of specific heat was formulated based on the (c_p) enhancement originating at the surface layer.

Chapter 5

Case Study 2 - Nano-Sphere

5.1 Simulation Details

For the simulation of isolated nano-systems with qualitative relevance to solid constituent to be added in nanofluids, 5 spherical nanoparticles (n_{sp}) with varying diameter were constructed. The atoms were arranged in a close packed face-centered cubic (*fcc*) array. The primitive lattice vectors are

$$\vec{a}_1 = a \times \left[\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 0 \right] \quad \vec{a}_2 = a \times \left[\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2} \right] \quad \vec{a}_3 = a \times \left[0, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right]$$

where lattice distance $a = 1.679$. Initial atomic positions were generated inside LAMMPS by defining spherical geometrical regions and filling with atoms maintaining the reduced density of $\rho = 0.8442$. The data in Table. 5.1 indicate relevant structural

Figure 5.1: Snapshots of the initial atomic configurations of (a) n_{sp1} , (b) n_{sp2} , (c) n_{sp3} , (d) n_{sp4} and (e) n_{sp5} sequentially. All samples have free surface in all spatial (x, y, z) direction.

details. The diameters of each n_{sp} samples has 6, 10, 20, 30 and 40 unit-cell length consecutively, when constructed. The input code is already given in the appendix

section 7.1.2. Snapshots of initial atomic configuration are displayed in following Fig. 5.1. The atoms in the n_{sp} interacts between each-other with an inter-atomic

	ϕ	η	N	Index
	10.07	0.472	381	n_{sp1}
	16.79	0.283	2099	n_{sp2}
Nano-sphere (n_{sp})	33.58	0.153	16751	n_{sp3}
	50.37	0.1	56435	n_{sp4}
	67.16	0.077	134000	n_{sp5}

Table 5.1: Studied Nano-spheres. Here ϕ is the diameter of the samples, N is the total number of atoms in each systems and η is the ratio between geometric surface atoms and total number of atoms.

potential having functional form of Eq. 3.1. With a spherical cutoff length $r_c = 2.8$, the interactions were truncated with a shift to 0.0. For the simulation of isolated nano-system (spheres), non-periodic boundary conditions were applied in all spatial directions. Simulation box sizes were kept sufficiently large in the all directions, to ensure zero interaction with the images of atoms. Equations of motions were integrated in canonical (NVT) ensemble conditions with a timestep size of 0.005. This allows the nano-particles to expand as a function of temperature under a zero pressure environment. Following the thermal cycling scheme shown in Fig. 4.2 with heating and cooling rate of 3.0×10^{-7} deg per MD steps, initial trajectories were relaxed at absolute energy-minimized state with restructured surface. This strategy ensures the accuracy of the quasi-continuous heating (see Fig. 3.4) for producing the thermal output at T -range $[T_1, T_2]$; where $T_1 = 0.01$ and $T_2 = 0.4$. Using the highlighted configuration of Fig. 4.2, all thermal and structural calculations were performed in previously mentioned temperature range with a linear heating rate of 1.3×10^{-7} deg per MD steps. Temperature was thermostatted every 100 simulation steps with Nosé-Hoover style time integrator (Hoover 1985). All LAMMPS codes for thermal cycling and production steps are mentioned in appendix 7.1.5 and 7.1.8. Necessary details of reference bulk system are already explained in previous section 4.1.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Structural Analysis

To characterize different features of structural information, cumulative density profiles of well-equilibrated n_{sp} configurations are depicted in Fig. 5.2. Each datum is averaged over full trajectories at $T = 0.15$. Since at this T , all atoms are packed in constant density layers, the roughness in the trends of smaller samples (n_{sp1} , n_{sp2}) are due to layer-by-layer oscillation of atomic positions. This tendency diminishes at the distance $\rightarrow \frac{\phi}{2}$ from the centre, due to fewer atoms present at outer spherical layers. Through oversampling of spatial bins this is avoided in the trends of larger samples (n_{sp3} , n_{sp4} and n_{sp5}), as the outer layers consists numerous atoms. As displayed with

Figure 5.2: Cumulative number density distributions of all n_{sp} samples at $T = 0.15$. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Black, red, blue, green and orange lines report cumulative density profiles of the n_{sp1} , n_{sp2} , n_{sp3} , n_{sp4} and n_{sp5} respectively.

details in Fig. 5.3, density profiles (a) along with cumulative distribution of atoms (b) inside n_{sp1} reveal the expansion of the systems with increasing T . From Fig. 5.3a, a non-linear increase of the n_{sp1} size was detected. This is consistent with previous findings for small finite systems due to strong surface-surface correlations (see Fig. 4.3 in previous chapter). Furthermore, the density peaks of Fig. 5.3b start to broaden with the rise of temperature, whilst long-range order at the surfaces were observed to be diminished at $T \geq 0.15$. The loss of structural orders at the surface can be linked to the formation of a quasi-liquid layers. These results corroborate previous findings in the cases of n_{sl} as well as in prior research (Dash et al. 2006), where the pre-melting originated at the surface. Analogous trends were also seen in other n_{sp} samples. With further explorations of cumulative density profiles, the distribution of

Figure 5.3: For n_{sp1} , detailed explorations of density profile trends at $T = 0.01$ (black), $T = 0.1$ (red), $T = 0.15$ (blue) and $T = 0.2$ (magenta). (a) Cumulative number density profile corroborates expansion of system with increasing temperature. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. (b) Local density profile rescaled over bulk density as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$. At $T = 0.01$ density peaks are well-defined, whereas with increasing temperature the peaks starts to broaden.

atoms inside of n_{sp3} and n_{sp5} are plotted in Fig. 5.4a and Fig. 5.4b respectively. In both cases, the reporting T of density profile were kept close to T_M to ensure the formation of homogeneously distributed quasi-liquid surface layers. With observations from previous Fig. 5.4 two regions have been identified: a solid-bulk region (where density scales with ϕ^3) and a quasi-liquid region (where density diverges from ϕ^3). These considerations give access to extract quantified measurements of quasi-liquid layer thickness. Although, this measurement criteria is invalid for systems too small in size (such as n_{sp1}), due to the absence of "true" bulk layers. Sets of the plots of the local density profiles for the sample n_{sp5} at low ($T = 0.01$) and high ($T = 0.3$) are shown in Fig. 5.5. At low $T = 0.01$, the profile consists sharp and well-resolved peaks. With enhanced atomic vibrations, the peak positions widen due to thermal expansion at $T = 0.3$. In the figure one can distinguish three regions: (1) a bulk region with the density oscillating around the average bulk density (at $T = 0.1$; (2) a region with density oscillating always below the bulk density, which is the interface region, and (3) a region of steep decrease of the density, which is the surface region. Similar behaviours were seen for the case of n_{sp3} and n_{sp4} as well while smaller systems (i.e. n_{sp1} and n_{sp2}) show disparity owing to strongly correlating surface and the absence of bulk layers. This generalization contrasts the behaviour of finite amorphous systems, where the interface region manifests a small "bump", as is much denser region (in comparison with average bulk density) characterized by harder phonons (Roder et al. 2001, Dagur 2020).

With local order Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis, better understanding of structural evolution can be achieved. In the Fig. 5.6, results of Ackland-Jones analysis are shown for the investigated n_{sp} . Smaller spheres n_{sp1} and n_{sp2} have *hcp* phases along *fcc* phases inside. During thermal cycling, some atoms prefer to go to energetically more favorable *hcp* structure (although the difference in cohesive energy is very small, $\equiv 0.01\%$) (Kihara & Koba 1952). With the increase of the size, the number of atoms having *hcp* structures decreased, ultimately going to zero in the cases of n_{sp4} and n_{sp5} . Intuitively, with increasing radius of curvature, the atoms have lesser degree of freedom. This helps to retain the original *fcc* structure, despite thermal

(b) Cumulative number density profile of n_{sp5} .

Figure 5.4: Cumulative number density profiles (red line) $T = 0.3$. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Inset shows deviation from cubic behaviour (blue line) in outer layers.

Figure 5.5: Local density profiles of n_{sp5} rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Blue (dashed) line illustrates the trend at $T = 0.01$ and red (solid) line describes the trend at $T = 0.3$. From the deviation of density from average value, three regions have been identified; 1 - Bulk region, 2 - Interface region and 3 - Surface region.

cycling. As seen from Table. 5.2, classification results from Ackland-Jones methods are summarized. Migration of inner (*fcc* or *hcp*) atoms to the surface layers were also seen with increasing number of atoms with *unknown* structures. With higher degree of freedom in smaller samples (such as n_{sp1} , n_{sp2}), the proportions of atoms migrating to the surface are higher comparing the bigger counterparts.

5.2.2 Phase Transition Analysis

After careful observations of temperature dependant structural information, using "flying atom" method, initiation of solid-to-gas phase transition were also located for all studied n_{sp} . Snapshots of few simulations when atoms leave the surface are displayed in Fig. 5.7. The numerical values of T_M as obtained from flying atom methods are tabulated in Table. 5.3. Although the findings contradict previous study of (Van

Figure 5.6: Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis of investigated systems. Green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms, blue colored atoms are inner *hcp* atoms and maroon colored atoms are surface atoms with unknown local structure of (a) n_{sp1} at $T = 0.01$, (b) n_{sp1} at $T = 0.2$, (c) n_{sp2} at $T = 0.01$, (d) n_{sp2} at $T = 0.2$, (e) n_{sp5} at $T = 0.01$ and (f) n_{sp5} at $T = 0.2$ consecutively. Different phonon modes can be seen emerging on the surface

		$T = 0.01$	$T = 0.2$
n_{sp1}	N_{fcc}	158	140
	N_{hcp}	39	38
	$N_{unknown}$	184	203
n_{sp2}	N_{fcc}	1348	1338
	N_{hcp}	157	118
	$N_{unknown}$	594	643
n_{sp3}	N_{fcc}	14195	14041
	N_{hcp}	0	0
	$N_{unknown}$	2556	2710
n_{sp4}	N_{fcc}	50633	50646
	N_{hcp}	0	0
	$N_{unknown}$	5802	5789
n_{sp5}	N_{fcc}	123671	123361
	N_{hcp}	0	0
	$N_{unknown}$	10329	10639

Table 5.2: Average number of surface (*unknown*) atoms, inner (*fcc*) atoms and (*hcp*) in all n_{sp} systems reported at $T = 0.01$ and $T = 0.2$. Estimated using Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis.

Sang et al. 2013) where they have assumed $T = 0.35$ to be the limit of thermal stability in a system similar to n_{sp2} . It could be argued that complete premelting guarantees the progression of continuous phase transition through layer-by-layer disorder. The smaller n_{sp} can be assumed close to a cluster due to the proportion of surface atoms and the T_M calculated here is in agreement with previous works on LJ clusters (Polak 2006). For further validation of previous criteria, additional self-

<i>Index</i>	T_M
n_{sp1}	0.295
n_{sp2}	0.32
n_{sp3}	0.34
n_{sp4}	0.35
n_{sp5}	0.35

Table 5.3: Solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) of all n_{sp} samples, derived from flying atom method

consistency check was performed by two phase non-equilibrium simulation. Initial atomic configurations with both solid and gas phases (see the Fig. 5.8a) were generated by providing a transient thermal shock to the solid configuration. Supplying sudden heat spike ensures the solid crystal seed to stay intact while atoms on the

(a) At $T = 0.295$, an atom leaving the surface of n_{sp1} .

(b) At $T = 0.32$, an atom leaving the surface of n_{sp2} .

Figure 5.7: Trajectories of the flying atoms. Using Ackland-Jones bond-angle method, atoms on the surfaces are marked with maroon color, blue colored atoms are inner *hcp* atoms while green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms. Path which the flying atoms follow are depicted with blue line.

surface to be sublimated. If the simulation is equilibrated at $T < T_M$ ($T = 0.295$ in this case), the structure will turn to solid phase (refer to Fig. 5.8b). While, at $T > T_M$ ($T = 0.315$ in this case) the system stays "gaseous" (see Fig. 5.8c). To reach the "full" gas phase, the simulation has to evolve for a sufficiently long period of time. The interval, $\Delta T = T_g - T_s$ is not ubiquitous, rather depends on the accuracy/closeness one wants to achieve. Detailed manifestation of solid-to-gas phase transition is demonstrated in Fig. 5.9. Although the $T_M(\Phi)$ grows with gradually reducing slope, the linear fit of the inverse T_M of n_{sp} shows saturation to bulk T_M , well in advance of reaching the "true" MD bulk (with $\eta = 0$) T_M (see Fig. 5.9b). With previous structural information indicating the formation of "liquid-like" layers on the surface, and surface influenced phase transition; supplemental authentication

Figure 5.8: Snapshots of n_{sp1} two phase non-equilibrium simulation at different temperature range

Figure 5.9: Detailed analysis of solid-to-gas phase transition temperature (T_M) behavior is plotted for different n_{sp} samples and compared with reference bulk. Triangular shaped data-points are T_M value identified from flying atom method. Error bar shows the determined ΔT from the evolution of two-phase non-equilibrium configuration. (a) shows progression of T_M as the diameter (Φ) increases. Black dashed line indicates bulk melting transition temperature $T = 0.56$ at $P = 0.001$. Blue dashed line is for a nearest-neighbor LJ solid model fitted melting temperature $T = 0.5$ at $P = 0$ reported elsewhere (Cowley 1983). In (b) abscissa reports inverse T_M as a function of surface atoms to total atom ratio η in the ordinate. Black and blue squares are denotations of bulk at $P = 0.001$ and $P = 0$ respectively, while red square is the extrapolated T_M of bulk from the linear fit.

were conducted by observing the resultant Cartesian component of the atomic mean squared displacements. While the same was performed on all n_{sp} samples, Fig. 5.10 shows msd evolution of two (n_{sp1} and n_{sp4}). The trends at $T = 0.1$ are rather indistinctive. When $T \rightarrow T_M$; surface layers always demonstrate typical "liquid-like" tendency. In contrast, the inner layers of n_{sp1} shows more 'liquid-like' oscillation at unlike the n_{sp4} counterpart. These results uphold previous findings in Fig. 5.3 apropos to the lack of "true" bulk layers inside.

(a) Total squared displacement of n_{sp1} at the surface layer. Behaviour of the bulk layer is shown in inset. At $T = 0.28$, surface behaves "liquid-like" along with bulk layer.

(b) Total squared displacement of n_{sp4} at the surface layer. Behaviour of the bulk layer is shown in inset. At $T = 0.31$, surface behaves "liquid-like" albeit bulk layer is "solid-like".

Figure 5.10: Mean squared displacement (msd) of two n_{sp} system, as a function of MD time-steps. Data are shown for T just below T_M and $T = 0.1$ (solid phase) for each nano-system.

5.2.3 Specific Heat Analysis

For the characterization of specific heat (c_p) in solid phase, primary analysis of $E_{Pot}(T)$ is displayed in Fig. 5.11. All except $E_{Pot}(n_{sp3})$ have non-linearity with quartic polynomial fitting. The reasons behind 5-th order polynomial fit for n_{sp3} data were to reduce the residual error and achieve better shape of c_p at low T region. The

Figure 5.11: Potential energy (E_{Pot}) of (a) n_{sp1} and (b) n_{sp3} , calculated over temperature range of $0.01 - T_M$ at $P = 0$. E_{Pot} is summed over N .

temperature controlled size dependence of c_p values are plotted in Fig. 5.12. Analytically solving the derivatives of MD E_{Pot} with Eq. 3.26, the values of $c_p(T)$ are obtained. Smaller systems, n_{sp1} and n_{sp2} have the highest enhancement in c_p , especially near transition; followed by n_{sp3} . Due to different polynomial fit, the $c_p(n_{sp3})$ is slightly biased at $T \rightarrow T_M$. Whereas, the plots of n_{sp4} and n_{sp5} are almost identical to each other. The shape of the c_p functions at very low temperature (say $T = 0.01$ to $T = 0.1$) are however highly influenced by the fitting parameters. By solving the differentials with piece-wise function, in principle, should yield better accuracy

Figure 5.12: Isobaric specific heat (c_p) of n_{sp1} (red), n_{sp2} (green), n_{sp3} (magenta), n_{sp4} (blue) and n_{sp5} (yellow) at $P = 0$, investigated in solid regime. The highest data-point corresponds to the solid-to-gas phase transition (T_M). For comparison, reference bulk data in shown in black. Inset - $c_p(T)$ rescaled over T_M .

at low T range. In an attempt to represent the systems in uniform thermodynamic scale, inset of Fig. 3.26 depicts $c_p(T/T_M)$. The trends are almost linear till $T = 0.6$, with divergence emerging prominently at $T/T_m > 0.7$. With surface pre-melting, which usually occurs around $0.7 - 0.8$ of T_M (Gómez et al. 2003), softening of surface phonons contribute to this enhancements.

5.3 Discussion

In this chapter, thermostatic properties of LJ-nanospheres have been investigated, with technological relevance to the curvature. Detailed structural information and evolution as a function of temperature were illustrated by several criteria; specifically - local and cumulative density profile, local structure order analysis with Ackland-Jones

method. Separation of "bulk-like" layers from "liquid-like" outer layers were observed to be nicely linked with the progression of temperature. In addition, predominant "softer" phonon modes were revealed in the surface. At smaller size nano-spheres, modulation of "soft" surface phonons dominate attributable to higher proportions.

Next, by calculating solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) with flying atom method, an generic idea of premelting along with the initiation of transition through surface were observed. Additionally, the two-phase non-equilibrium simulation validated the previous criteria of phase transition to be a sound one. Continuum atomic mean-square displacements reveled the formation of "liquid" layer on the surface of all nanospheres, when temperature crossed a certain threshold. Intuitively, a similar empirical criterion like in the case of curvature-free finite system could exist for curved finite system as well. Further investigation is required to approve or discard such considerations.

Regardless of the fact that the microscopic mechanism of premelting is not fully understood, it is of interest to obtain qualitative information on the response behavior of thermodynamic properties due to these effects. Specific heat, c_p of studied systems are found to be increasing with temperature and strongly size-dependent; that is smaller system will have higher enhancements in c_p comparing bulk counterpart. The amount of increment arise from the "soft" surface phonons, and is dependent on the system-specific proportions of surface atoms. Thermodynamically, the specific heat is very nicely linked to the extensive physical quantities, but is introduced and defined as the derivative of the E_{Pot} . The role of E_{Pot} , better determined from MD, influences the shape of the specific heat function on physical (specific heat has to strongly increase at low T , almost flatten at intermediate T , sharp increase close to T_M) and numerical (residuals of the fits) grounds.

Chapter 6

Case Study 3 - Hollow Nano-Shell

Conceptually hollow nano-shells (n_{sh}) are generalization of annuli to three dimensions. The volume of the active region is between two concentric spheres with diameter ϕ_{out} and ϕ_{in} ,

$$V = \frac{\pi}{6} \times (\phi_{out}^3 - \phi_{in}^3) \quad (6.1)$$

where $\frac{1}{2}(\phi_{out} - \phi_{in}) = t$, thickness of the shell. These (n_{sh}) have technological relevance in latent heat thermal energy storage (see in Fig. 1.1). Comparing with sensible heat storage, it has higher energy storage density (Sarbu & Sebarchievici 2018). By encapsulating phase-change material (PCM) inside these n_{sh} , the specific surface area increases (Nithyanandam et al. 2017). This leads to higher specific heat. In this chapter, the n_{sh} (in absence of any PCM inside) have been studied to understand qualitative structural evolution alongside the specific heat changes over a wide temperature range.

6.1 Simulation Details

Two samples of n_{sh} were prepared with atoms arranged in face-centered cubic(*fcc*) structure. The initial configurations were generated by filling the volume ($\frac{\pi}{6}\phi_{out}^3$) with reduced density of $\rho = 0.8442$ and then removing atoms from spherical region where distance from the centre is $(\phi_{out}/2 - t)$. Input code for LAMMPS is given in the appendix section 7.1.3. Both samples have equal outer surface area, while the shell

	ϕ_{out}	t	N	η	Index
Hollow nano-shell (n_{sh})	26.864	5.037	6343	0.367	n_{sh1}
	26.864	6.716	7531	0.269	n_{sh2}

Table 6.1: Studied Hollow nano-shells. Here ϕ_{out} is the outer diameter of the samples, t is the shell thickness, N is the total number of atoms in each systems and η is the ratio between geometric surface atoms and total number of atoms (in this case the systems have two surface regions - one surface is trapped inside while other one is free).

Figure 6.1: Snapshots of the initial atomic configurations of (a) n_{sh2} and (b) n_{sh1} . Both samples have free surface in all spatial (x, y, z) directions.

thickness(t) changed thus altering the inner surface area. Necessary structural details are presented in Table. 6.1, Some snapshots of initial atomic positions are shown in Fig. 6.1. The atoms have interaction as defined by Eq. 3.1. The potential has a spherical cutoff length of $r_c = 2.8$ with truncation shift to 0.0. The simulation box is sufficiently large with non-periodic boundary conditions in all spatial directions; this ensures simulation of isolated finite system with no interaction from periodic images. The simulations were performed in canonical (NVT) ensemble condition with a timestep size of 0.005. Similar thermal cycling as elucidated in previous chapters were also performed following the method in Fig. 4.2. From the absolute energy-minimized atomic configuration, production of thermal and structural outputs were performed following the quasi-continuous heating methods at a range of $T = 0.01$ to $T = 0.4$. The temperature was increased at a rate of 1.3×10^{-7} deg per MD steps. Nosé-Hoover style time integrator (Hoover 1985) was used to thermostat every 100 simulation steps. All necessary input codes for LAMMPS are listed in appendix section 7.1.6 and 7.1.9.

6.2 Results

6.2.1 Structural Analysis

Figure 6.2: Cumulative number density distributions of all n_{sh} samples at $T = 0.15$. Ordinate reports N^* - distribution of the atoms re-scaled over N , as a function of $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa. Black and red lines report cumulative density profiles of the n_{sh1} and n_{sh2} respectively.

To characterize the structural properties and determine the size and thickness of n_{sh} , Fig. 6.2 portrays the cumulative distribution of particles inside the spherical shells. While the largest datum in the abscissa represents the diameters of each samples, width of the distribution is the corresponding thicknesses. The plot shows similar cubic growth as seen in previous spherical nanoparticles. For better interpretation of layering inside the spherical shells, the local density profiles of n_{sh1} and n_{sh2} are depicted in Fig. 6.3 and Fig. 6.4. The profiles are very unlike. For the case of n_{sh1} it evidently lacks of symmetry; as the deviations from average bulk density

Figure 6.3: Local density profile of n_{sh1} at $T = 0.25$ rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa, where t is the thickness of the spherical shell. From the deviation of density from average value (green dashed line), five regions have been identified; 1 - internal surface region, 2 - internal interface region, 3 - internal bulk region, 4 - external interface region and 5 - external surface region. Blue (solid) line illustrates the rescaled cumulative distribution trend; only region 3 (internal bulk region) follows the cubic growth (sky blue dashed line).

shows gradual lowering followed by a steep decrease, inner surface shows very unique shoulder-like formation. This "pile-up" of atoms is possibly due to strongly correlated surfaces. The density peaks inside bulk region are also comparatively broader, indicating the lack of "true" bulk layering. In contrast, n_{sh2} profile shows distinctive density oscillations, with sharp peaks defining inner bulk region and strong decline in the surface regions. While the interface and surface regions are indistinguishable from the profile (similar was seen in the case of n_{sl} . See Fig. 4.6b), the surface layers are almost symmetrical.

With Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis, tabulated numerical data (in Table. 6.2) of different crystal structures emerging from temperature evolution indicate similar thickening of surface-interface regions. Further to visualize the organisations of differ-

Figure 6.4: Local density profile of n_{sh2} at $T = 0.25$ rescaled over bulk density with $\frac{\phi}{2}$ in the abscissa, where t is the thickness of the spherical shell. From the deviation of density from average value (green dashed line), three regions have been identified; 1 - internal surface region, 2 - internal bulk region and 3 - external surface region. Blue (solid) line illustrates the rescaled cumulative distribution trend; only region 2 (internal bulk region) follows the cubic growth (sky blue dashed line).

		$T = 0.01$	$T = 0.25$
n_{sh1}	N_{fcc}	4016	3736
	N_{hcp}	0	62
	$N_{unknown}$	2327	2545
n_{sh2}	N_{fcc}	5506	5321
	N_{hcp}	0	25
	$N_{unknown}$	2025	2185

Table 6.2: Average number of surface (*unknown*) atoms, inner (*fcc*) atoms and (*hcp*) in all n_{sh} systems reported at $T = 0.01$ and $T = 0.2$. Estimated using Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis

ent solid phases and emerging phonon modes on the surfaces, Fig. 6.5 shows snapshots from the simulations with different colored atoms indicating different local structures.

Figure 6.5: Ackland-Jones bond-angle analysis of investigates systems. Green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms, blue colored atoms are inner *hcp* atoms and maroon colored atoms are surface atoms with unknown local structure of (a) n_{sh1} at $T = 0.01$, (b) n_{sh1} at $T = 0.25$, (c) n_{sh2} at $T = 0.01$ and (d) n_{sh2} at $T = 0.25$. Different phonon modes can be seen emerging on the surfaces.

6.2.2 Phase Transition Analysis

To see the solid-to-gas phase transitions of n_{sh} , the "flying atom" method were employed. Fig. 6.6 illustrates the trajectories of the leaving atoms. Also, the recorded T at which the atoms leave the surface are presented in Table. 6.3. While further

<i>Index</i>	T_M
n_{sh1}	0.345
n_{sh2}	0.345

Table 6.3: Solid-to-gas transition temperature (T_M) of all n_{sh} samples, derived from flying atom method

consistence checks were not conducted, the T_M calculated from flying-atom method, is similar to that of n_{sl} . It was inspected visually that: liquid layers formed on the inner surface are more mobile.

6.2.3 Specific Heat Analysis

To calculate the specific heat (c_p) functions, focusing on the solid, $E_{Pot}(T)$ were analysed numerically. The plots of $E_{Pot}(T)$ are presented in following Fig. 6.7. The

Figure 6.6: Trajectories of the flying atoms. Using Ackland-Jones bond-angle method, atoms on the surfaces are marked with maroon color, blue colored atoms are inner *hcp* atoms while green colored atoms are inner *fcc* atoms. Path which the flying atoms follow are depicted with blue line.

Figure 6.7: Potential energy (E_{Pot}) of (a) n_{sh1} and (b) n_{sh2} , calculated over temperature range of $0.01 - T_M$ at $P = 0$. E_{Pot} is summed over N .

function grows non-linearly with 4-th order polynomial fit. Now to understand the temperature and size-dependence of c_p , the values are plotted in Fig. 6.8. While the c_p seems to increase with reduced thickness, the shape of the trends are very much similar at intermediate T to high T (say close to T_M). The $c_p(n_{sp1})$ has distortion at lower T region, this could be avoided by performing piece-wise differentiation of $E_{Pot}(n_{sh1})$. The rescaled $c_p(T/T_M)$ of both samples start deviating from bulk c_p at around $T = 0.5T_M$. As this deviation is linked to the emergence of softer phonon modes, the surface premelting or the formation of quasi-liquid layers on the both surfaces start around 20% before the solid spherical nanoparticle counterparts. Instead when these values are compared with nanoslabs, one can attain perfect correspondence.

Figure 6.8: Isobaric specific heat (c_p) of n_{sh1} (red) and n_{sh2} (green) at $P = 0$, investigated in solid regime. The highest data-point corresponds to the solid-to-gas phase transition (T_M). For comparison, reference bulk data in shown in black. Inset - $c_p(T)$ rescaled over T_M .

6.3 Discussion

In this chapter two finite hollow-spheres were primarily studied, focusing on potential usage as a sensible-heat storage material i.e. to encapsulate PCM inside. Initial structural characterizations indicate absence of bulk layer inside very thin hollow-spheres. Although the curvature is present in inside and outside, the density profile of thicker hollow-sphere shows similarity with a system having flat surface. While temperature influenced layer-by-layer modulation of density were not investigated, local structure analysis indicates formation of quasi-liquid layer on both surfaces. The thickness of such layers are asymmetrical, such as internal surface is much thinner.

Solid-to-gas phase transition results are in agreement with previous finite, samples where the higher limit of transition temperature seems to be saturating at a certain value. The specific heat of both hollow-spheres demonstrated increasing behaviours typical of any finite system. The shapes of the functions are depends only on the fitting parameter, to achieve the best fit, polynomial with the lowest residual is recommended.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Scope

The main original results of this thesis are as follows,

1. For planar nano-structures, thermal expansion is non-linear so long as the both surfaces are correlated. With the decay in correlation length, systems behave on a level of equivalence with bulk counterpart. Solid-to-gas phase transition initiates at the surface with local disorders (by forming quasi-liquid layers); and advances with layer-by layer modulation from outside to inside. While the finite system always undergoes transition well below from the bulk value, if the surfaces are uncorrelated (far from each other), initiation point of such transition is independent of size. Most importantly, surface phonons are not system-influenced, and universal description of phonon-mediated phase-transition has been proposed. Specific heat was found to be size-dependent and for planar nano-structure it scales linearly with the surface.
2. For spherical nano-structures, separation of "bulk" and "liquid" layers are nicely linked with the temperature. Different regions are easily distinguishable from the density oscillation of layers. For smaller size systems, bulk layers were absent and surface phonons dominated the attributes. Continuum atomic mean-square displacements revealed the formation of "liquid" layer on the surface of all nano-spheres, when temperature crossed a certain threshold. With the evolution of local structure and deviation from ideal situation, thickness of surface layers

were numerically evaluated. Phase transition was found to be strongly dependent on the curvature while, after certain radius of curvature, the behaviour was analogous to the planar counter part. Specific heat of studied systems were found to be increasing with temperature and strongly size-dependent.

3. For spherical hollow nanostructures, systems have a more closer correspondence to planar finite systems than to solid spherical counterpart. The particulars of surface layers are dependent on the shell thickness and are not influenced by curvature. Initiation temperature of phase transition is similar to flat nanostructure and was found to be independent with system size. Specific heat had a increasing trend with smaller size system having higher enhancement.

All the investigated systems show an increase of the specific heat as compared to that of the bulk system. If the specific heat are compared as a function of T/T_M , a systematic trend is found with a larger increase for the smaller nano-sizes. The specific heat increase is correlated to the decrease of the interface density and to the corresponding appearance of thermal modes able to store more efficiently the heat, the softer surface phonons, which, clearly, are not present in bulk systems. From this results a generic criteria for the heat capacity enhancement in solid phase is that - Curved finite system will have higher enhancement in the specific heat and smaller size nanoparticles will have higher heat capacity.

In conclusion, some interesting directions of further development of this work could be

1. Calculation of pair correlation functions for finite systems and study structural evolution.
2. Formulate Hansen-Verlet "like" freezing criteria for finite systems.
3. Extend proposed "Lindemann-like" criteria of vibration amplitude to curved surfaces.
4. Extended comparison with non-crystalline nanomaterials.

Bibliography

Ackland, G. J. & Jones, A. P. (2006), ‘Applications of local crystal structure measures in experiment and simulation’, *Physical Review B* **73**(5), 054104.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.73.054104>

Alarifi, H. A., Atiş, M., Özdoğan, C., Hu, A., Yavuz, M. & Zhou, Y. (2013), ‘Determination of complete melting and surface premelting points of silver nanoparticles by molecular dynamics simulation’, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **117**(23), 12289–12298.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp311541c>

Alder, B. J. & Wainwright, T. E. (1957), ‘Phase Transition for a Hard Sphere System’, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **27**(5), 1208–1209.

URL: <http://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/1.1743957>

Alder, B. J. & Wainwright, T. E. (1959), ‘Studies in Molecular Dynamics. I. General Method’, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **31**(2), 459–466.

URL: <http://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/1.1730376>

Allen, M. P. & Tildesley, D. J. (2017), *Computer Simulation of Liquids*, 2nd edn, Oxford University Press, Inc., USA.

Arthur, O. & Karim, M. (2016), ‘An investigation into the thermophysical and rheological properties of nanofluids for solar thermal applications’, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **55**, 739–755.

URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.10.065>

Bolmatov, D., Brazhkin, V. V. & Trachenko, K. (2012), ‘The phonon theory of liquid thermodynamics’, *Scientific Reports* **2**(1), 421.

URL: <http://www.nature.com/articles/srep00421>

Bolmatov, D. & Trachenko, K. (2011), ‘Liquid heat capacity in the approach from the solid state: Anharmonic theory’, *Physical Review B* **84**(5), 054106.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.84.054106>

Brenner, D. (2000), ‘The art and science of an analytic potential’, *physica status solidi (b)* **217**(1), 23–40.

Brovchenko, I., Geiger, A. & Oleinikova, A. (2005), ‘Surface critical behavior of fluids: Lennard-jones fluid near a weakly attractive substrate’, *The European Physical Journal B* **44**(3), 345–358.

Chakravarty, C., Debenedetti, P. G. & Stillinger, F. H. (2007), ‘Lindemann measures for the solid-liquid phase transition’, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **126**(20), 204508.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2737054>

Cotterill, R. M. J. (1975), ‘Melting-point depression in very thin lennard-jones crystals’, *The Philosophical Magazine: A Journal of Theoretical Experimental and Applied Physics* **32**(6), 1283–1288.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786437508228108>

Cowley, E. R. (1983), ‘Some monte carlo calculations for the lennard-jones solid’, *Phys. Rev. B* **28**, 3160–3163.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.28.3160>

D’Aguanno, B., Karthik, M., Grace, A. N. & Floris, A. (2018), ‘Thermostatic properties of nitrate molten salts and their solar and eutectic mixtures’, *Scientific Reports* **8**(1), 10485.

URL: <http://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-018-28641-1>

- Dagur, D. S. (2020), Molecular dynamics simulation of nanoparticles for energy storage and biomedical application, Master's thesis, Vellore Institute of Technology, India.
- Damyanova, M., Zarkova, L. & Hohm, U. (2009), 'Effective intermolecular interaction potentials of gaseous fluorine, chlorine, bromine, and iodine', *International Journal of Thermophysics* **30**(4), 1165–1178.
- Dash, J. G. (1999), 'History of the search for continuous melting', *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **71**, 1737–1743.
URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/RevModPhys.71.1737>
- Dash, J. G., Rempel, A. W. & Wettlaufer, J. S. (2006), 'The physics of premelted ice and its geophysical consequences', *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **78**, 695–741.
URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/RevModPhys.78.695>
- Duffie, J. A. & Beckman, W. A. (2013), *Solar Engineering of Thermal Processes*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, NJ, USA.
URL: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/9781118671603>
- Engelmann, S. & Hentschke, R. (2019), 'Specific heat capacity enhancement studied in silica doped potassium nitrate via molecular dynamics simulation', *Scientific Reports* **9**(1), 7606.
URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-44132-3>
- Fan, X., Pan, D. & Li, M. (2020), 'Rethinking lindemann criterion: A molecular dynamics simulation of surface mediated melting', *Acta Materialia* **193**, 280 – 290.
URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1359645420303529>
- Frantz, D. D. (2001), 'Magic number behavior for heat capacities of medium-sized classical lennard-jones clusters', *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **115**(13), 6136–6157.
URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1397329>

Frenkel, J. (1946), *Kinetic Theory of Liquids*, International Series of Monographs on Physics, Oxford: Clarendon Press.

Frenken, J. W. M., Marée, P. M. J. & van der Veen, J. F. (1986), ‘Observation of surface-initiated melting’, *Phys. Rev. B* **34**, 7506–7516.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.34.7506>

Frenken, J. W. M., Toennies, J. P. & Wöll, C. (1988), ‘Self-diffusion at a melting surface observed by he scattering’, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **60**, 1727–1730.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.60.1727>

Frenken, J. W. M. & Veen, J. F. v. d. (1985), ‘Observation of surface melting’, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **54**, 134–137.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.54.134>

Gao, J., Ndong, R. S., Shiflett, M. B. & Wagner, N. J. (2015), ‘Creating Nanoparticle Stability in Ionic Liquid [C 4 mim][BF 4] by Inducing Solvation Layering’, *ACS Nano* **9**(3), 3243–3253.

URL: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsnano.5b00354>

Gaston, N. (2018), ‘Cluster melting: new, limiting, and liminal phenomena’, *Advances in Physics: X* **3**(1), 1401487.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23746149.2017.1401487>

Generalic, E. (2018), ‘Lennard-jones potential’. [Croatian-English Chemistry Dictionary & Glossary. KTF-Split; Accessed: 11 April 2020].

URL: <https://glossary.periodni.com>

Gibbs, J. W. (1902), *Elementary Principles in Statistical Mechanics*, Charles Scribner’s Sons.

URL: <https://archive.org/details/elementaryprinc00gibbgoog>

Gómez, L., Dobry, A., Geuting, C., Diep, H. T. & Burakovsky, L. (2003), ‘Dislocation lines as the precursor of the melting of crystalline solids observed in monte carlo

simulations’, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **90**, 095701.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.90.095701>

Haile, J. (1992), *Molecular Dynamics Simulation: Elementary Methods*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Hakkinen, H. & Landman, U. (1993), ‘Superheating, melting, and annealing of copper surfaces’, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **71**, 1023–1026.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.71.1023>

Hanszen, K. J. (1960), ‘Theoretische Untersuchungen über den Schmelzpunkt kleiner Kügelchen’, *Zeitschrift für Physik* **157**(5), 523–553.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01340711>

Heinz, H., Vaia, R. A., Farmer, B. L. & Naik, R. R. (2008), ‘Accurate simulation of surfaces and interfaces of face-centered cubic metals using 12-6 and 9-6 lennard-jones potentials’, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **112**(44), 17281–17290.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp801931d>

Heiser, G. A. (1984), Molecular dynamics calculation of mean square displacement in alkali metals and rare gas solids and comparison with lattice dynamics, Master’s thesis, Brock University.

URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10464/1966>

Hentschke, R. (2016), ‘On the specific heat capacity enhancement in nanofluids’, *Nanoscale Research Letters* **11**(1), 88.

URL: <http://www.nanoscalereslett.com/content/11/1/88>

Hockney, R. W. & Eastwood, J. W. (1988), *Computer Simulation Using Particles*, Taylor & Francis, Inc., USA.

Hoover, W. G. (1985), ‘Canonical dynamics: Equilibrium phase-space distributions’, *Physical Review A* **31**(3), 1695–1697.

Humphrey, W., Dalke, A. & Schulten, K. (1996), ‘VMD: Visual molecular dynamics’, *Journal of Molecular Graphics* **14**(1), 33–38.

URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0263785596000185>

IRENA (2019), *Global energy transformation: A roadmap to 2050 (2019 edition)*, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi.

Jones, J. (1924), ‘On the determination of molecular fields. —II. From the equation of state of a gas’, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character* **106**(738), 463–477.

URL: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rspa.1924.0082>

Karthik, M., Faik, A. & D’Aguanno, B. (2017), ‘Graphite foam as interpenetrating matrices for phase change paraffin wax: A candidate composite for low temperature thermal energy storage’, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **172**, 324–334.

URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0927024817304427>

Karthik, M., Faik, A., Doppiu, S., Roddatis, V. & D’Aguanno, B. (2015), ‘A simple approach for fabrication of interconnected graphitized macroporous carbon foam with uniform mesopore walls by using hydrothermal method’, *Carbon* **87**, 434–443.

URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0008622315001591>

Kihara, T. & Koba, S. (1952), ‘Crystal structures and intermolecular forces of rare gases’, *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan* **7**(4), 348–354.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1143/JPSJ.7.348>

Kim, W., Wang, R. & Majumdar, A. (2007), ‘Nanostructuring expands thermal limits’, *Nano Today* **2**(1), 40–47.

URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S174801320770018X>

Lacks, D. J. & Shukla, R. C. (1996), ‘Molecular dynamics and higher-order perturbation-theory results for the anharmonic free energy and equation of state of a lennard-jones solid’, *Phys. Rev. B* **54**, 3266–3272.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.54.3266>

LAMMPS website (n.d.).

URL: <http://lammmps.sandia.gov>

Landa, A., Häkkinen, H., Barnett, R., Wynblatt, P. & Landman, U. (1996), ‘Molecular dynamics study of disordering, roughening, and premelting of the pb(110) surface’, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **205-207**, 767 – 771.

URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022309396003043>

Leimkuhler, B. & Matthews, C. (2015), *Molecular Dynamics : With Deterministic and Stochastic Numerical Methods*, 1 edn, Springer International Publishing.

Li, M. & Johnson, W. L. (1992), ‘Fluctuations and thermodynamic response functions in a lennard-jones solid’, *Phys. Rev. B* **46**, 5237–5241.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.46.5237>

Lindemann, F. A. (1910), ‘über die berechnung molekulaner eigenfrequenzen’, *Physikalische Zeitschrift* **11**(14), 609–612.

Löwen, H. (1994), ‘Melting, freezing and colloidal suspensions’, *Physics Reports* **237**(5), 249 – 324.

URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0370157394900175>

Ma, Z., Kyotani, T., Liu, Z., Terasaki, O. & Tomita, A. (2001), ‘Very High Surface Area Microporous Carbon with a Three-Dimensional Nano-Array Structure: Synthesis and Its Molecular Structure’, *Chemistry of Materials* **13**(12), 4413–4415.

URL: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/cm010730l>

Mamedov, B. & Somuncu, E. (2014), ‘Analytical treatment of second virial coefficient over lennard-jones (2n-n) potential and its application to molecular systems’, *Journal of Molecular Structure* **1068**, 164–169.

URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022286014003597>

Martin, T. P., Näher, U., Schaber, H. & Zimmermann, U. (1994), ‘Evidence for a size-dependent melting of sodium clusters’, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*

100(3), 2322–2324.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.466530>

Mcbride, B. J., Gordon, S. & Reno, M. A. (1993), Coefficients for calculating thermodynamic and transport properties of individual species, Technical Report NASA-TM-4513, E-7981, NAS 1.15:4513, NASA Lewis Research Center, Cleveland, OH, United States.

McDonald, I. R. & Singer, K. (1967), ‘Calculation of thermodynamic properties of liquid argon from lennard-jones parameters by a monte carlo method’, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.* **43**, 40–49.

URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/DF9674300040>

McQuarrie, D. A. (1976), *Statistical Mechanics*, Harper & Row, New York.

Meijer, E. J. & Frenkel, D. (1991), ‘Melting line of yukawa system by computer simulation’, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **94**(3), 2269–2271.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.459898>

Multidisciplinary University Research Initiative, . (2012), ‘High Operating Temperature Fluids Funding Opportunity Announcement’, *US Department of Energy DE-FOA-0000567*, 9.

Murphy, C., Sun, Y., Cole, W., Maclaurin, G., Turchi, C. & Mehos, M. (2019), ‘The Potential Role of Concentrating Solar Power within the Context of DOE’s 2030 Solar Cost Targets’, *NREL Technical Report - NREL/TP-6A20-71912* (January).

URL: <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy19osti/71912.pdf>

Nithyanandam, K., Stekli, J. & Pitchumani, R. (2017), 10 - high-temperature latent heat storage for concentrating solar thermal (cst) systems, *in* M. J. Blanco & L. R. Santigosa, eds, ‘Advances in Concentrating Solar Thermal Research and Technology’, Woodhead Publishing Series in Energy, Woodhead Publishing, pp. 213 – 246.

URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780081005163000101>

Ohnesorge, R., Löwen, H. & Wagner, H. (1994), ‘Density functional theory of crystal-fluid interfaces and surface melting’, *Phys. Rev. E* **50**, 4801–4809.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevE.50.4801>

Plimpton, S. (1995), ‘Fast Parallel Algorithms for Short-Range Molecular Dynamics’, *Journal of Computational Physics* **117**(1), 1–19.

URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S002199918571039X>

Polak, W. (2006), ‘Size dependence of freezing temperature and structure instability in simulated Lennard-Jones clusters’, *The European Physical Journal D - Atomic, Molecular, Optical and Plasma Physics* **40**(2), 231–242.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjd/e2006-00145-8>

Pretti, E., Zerze, H., Song, M., Ding, Y., Mao, R. & Mittal, J. (2019), ‘Size-dependent thermodynamic structural selection in colloidal crystallization’, *Science Advances* **5**(9).

URL: <https://advances.sciencemag.org/content/5/9/eaaw5912>

Rapaport, D. C. (2004), *The Art of Molecular Dynamics Simulation*, 2 edn, Cambridge University Press.

Riazi, H., Murphy, T., Webber, G. B., Atkin, R., Tehrani, S. S. M. & Taylor, R. A. (2016), ‘Specific heat control of nanofluids: A critical review’, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences* **107**, 25–38.

URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S129007291630103X>

Roder, A., Kob, W. & Binder, K. (2001), ‘Structure and dynamics of amorphous silica surfaces’, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **114**(17), 7602–7614.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1360257>

Samsonov, V. M., Kharechkin, S. S., Gafner, S. L., Redel’, L. V. & Gafner, Y. Y. (2009), ‘Molecular dynamics study of the melting and crystallization of nanoparticles’, *Crystallography Reports* **54**(3), 526–531.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063774509030250>

Sarbu, I. & Sebarchievici, C. (2018), 'A comprehensive review of thermal energy storage', *Sustainability* **10**(2), 191.

SARKAR, S., JANA, C. & BAGCHI, B. (2017), 'Breakdown of universal Lindemann criterion in the melting of Lennard-Jones polydisperse solids', *Journal of Chemical Sciences* **129**(7), 833–840.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12039-017-1245-y>

Schneider, R., Sharma, A. R. & Rai, A. (2008), 'Introduction to molecular dynamics', pp. 3–40.

Shin, D. & Banerjee, D. (2011), 'Enhanced Specific Heat of Silica Nanofluid', *Journal of Heat Transfer* **133**(2).

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4002600>

Smith, J. C. (2017), 'A Major Player: Renewables Are Now Mainstream [Guest Editorial]', *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine* **15**(6), 16–21.

URL: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8070481/>

Stukowski, A. (2010), 'Visualization and analysis of atomistic simulation data with OVITO-the Open Visualization Tool', *MODELLING AND SIMULATION IN MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING* **18**(1).

Swope, W. C., Andersen, H. C., Berens, P. H. & Wilson, K. R. (1982), 'A computer simulation method for the calculation of equilibrium constants for the formation of physical clusters of molecules: Application to small water clusters', *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **76**(1), 637–649.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.442716>

Thi Thuy Huong, T., Van Hoang, V. & Ngoc Khuong Cat, P. (2014), 'Molecular dynamics simulations of crystallization of Lennard-Jones nanoparticles', *The European Physical Journal Applied Physics* **67**(1), 10402.

URL: <http://www.epjap.org/10.1051/epjap/2014140033>

Trachenko, K. & Brazhkin, V. V. (2016), 'Collective modes and thermodynamics of the liquid state', *Reports on Progress in Physics* **79**(1), 016502.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/79/1/016502>

Travasset, A. (2014), 'Phase diagram of power law and lennard-jones systems: Crystal phases', *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **141**(16), 164501.

URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4898371>

Trayanov, A. & Tosatti, E. (1988), 'Lattice theory of surface melting', *Phys. Rev. B* **38**, 6961–6974.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.38.6961>

Van de Waal, B. W. (1991), 'Can the Lennard-Jones solid be expected to be fcc?', *Physical Review Letters* **67**(23), 3263–3266.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.67.3263>

Van Sang, L., Van Hoang, V. & Thuy Hang, N. T. (2013), 'Molecular dynamics simulation of melting of fcc Lennard-Jones nanoparticles', *The European Physical Journal D* **67**(3), 64.

URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1140/epjd/e2013-30584-9>

Verlet, L. (1967), 'Computer "experiments" on classical fluids. i. thermodynamical properties of lennard-jones molecules', *Phys. Rev.* **159**, 98–103.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.159.98>

Wallace, D. C. (1991), 'Melting of elements', *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A: Mathematical and Physical Sciences* **433**(1889), 631–661.

URL: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/abs/10.1098/rspa.1991.0068>

Wette, F. D., Fowler, L. & Nijboer, B. (1971), 'Lattice dynamics, thermal expansion and specific heat of a lennard-jones solid in the quasi-harmonic approximation', *Physica* **54**(2), 292 – 304.

URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0031891471900279>

Wierschem, K. & Manousakis, E. (2011), 'Simulation of melting of two-dimensional lennard-jones solids', *Phys. Rev. B* **83**, 214108.

URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.83.214108>

Wu, X.-M., Wang, L., Tan, Z.-C., Li, G.-H. & Qu, S.-S. (2001), 'Preparation, characterization, and low-temperature heat capacities of nanocrystalline tio2 ultrafine powder', *Journal of Solid State Chemistry* **156**(1), 220 – 224.

URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022459600989916>

Zhou, Z., Zhang, H., Zhou, Y., Qiao, H., Gurung, A., Naderi, R., Elbohy, H., Smirnova, A. L., Lu, H., Chen, S. & Qiao, Q. (2017), 'Binder Free Hierarchical Mesoporous Carbon Foam for High Performance Lithium Ion Battery', *Scientific Reports* **7**(1), 1440.

URL: <http://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-01638-y>

Appendix

7.1 LAMMPS inputs scripts

7.1.1 Generation of initial atomic positions - Nano-slab

```
#----- 3d LJ nanoslab: datafile_generation -----  
#-----Initialization -----  
units          lj  
boundary       f p p  
atom_style     atomic  
#-----Simulation-box-definition-----  
lattice        fcc 0.8442  
region         box block 0 100 0 10 0 10  
create_box     1 box  
#-----Defining a slab-change xlo, xhi-according no. of  
unit-cells----  
lattice        fcc 0.8442  
region         1 block 49 51 INF INF INF INF  
create_atoms   1 region 1  
mass           1 1.0  
velocity       all create 0.01 87087 dist gaussian  
#-----Define Interaction-----  
pair_style     lj/cut 2.8  
pair_coeff     1 1 1.0 1.0
```

```
#-----Writing of the data file---
write_data      data.lj_np_slab
run             0
```

7.1.2 Generation of initial atomic positions - Nano-sphere

```
#---3d LJ nanosphere-datafile_generation---
#-----Initialization -----
units          lj
boundary       f f f
atom_style     atomic
#-----Simulation-box-definition-----
lattice        fcc 0.8442
region         box block 0 100 0 100 0 100
create_box     1 box
#-----Defining a sphere-----
lattice        fcc 0.8442
region         1 sphere 50 50 50 5 side in
create_atoms   1 region 1
mass           1 1.0
velocity       all create 0.01 87087 dist gaussian
#-----Define Interaction-----
pair_style     lj/cut 2.8
pair_coeff     1 1 1.0 1.0
#-----Writing of the data file---
write_data     data.lj_np_sphere
run           0
```

7.1.3 Generation of initial atomic positions - Hollow nano-shell

```
#--- 3d LJ hollow nanoshell - datafile_generation ---
#-----Initialization -----
units          lj
dimension      3
boundary       f f f
atom_style     atomic
#-----simulation-box-Definition-----
region         box block 0 100 0 100 0 100
create_box     1 box
#-----Defining_outer_sphere-----
lattice        fcc 0.8442
region         1 sphere 50 50 50 8 side in
create_atoms   1 region 1
#-----Defining inner_sphere-----
lattice        fcc 0.8442
region         2 sphere 50 50 50 4 side in
create_atoms   1 region 2
#-----Assigning mass and velocities-----
mass           1 1.0
delete_atoms   region 2 compress yes
velocity       all create 0.01 87087 dist gaussian
reset_ids
# ----- Define Interaction -----
pair_style     lj/cut 2.8
pair_coeff     1 1 1.0 1.0
#-----writing of the data file-----
write_data     data.lj_np_hollow
run           0
```

7.1.4 Thermal cycling of Nano-slab

```

#----- 3d LJ : Thermal Cycling -----
#-----Initialization -----
units          lj
dimension      3
boundary       f p p
atom_style     atomic
#-----System-Definition-----
read_data      data.lj_np_slab
# ----- Define Interaction -----
pair_style     lj/cut 2.8
pair_modify    shift yes
pair_coeff     * * 1.0 1.0
#-----Neighbor list-----
neighbor       0.3 bin
neigh_modify   every 1 delay 0 check yes
#-----Print-output----
restart        500 lj_slab_restart_1 lj_slab_restart_2
thermo_style   custom step ke pe etotal enthalpy temp pxx
               pyy pzz lx ly lz
thermo         50
#-----Dynamics-----
timestep       0.005
#-----Equilibration-----
fix            1 all npt temp 0.01 0.01 0.5 y 0.0 0.0 1.0 z
               0.0 0.0 1.0
run            500000
unfix         1
#-----Slow-Heating----

```

```

fix          1 all npt temp 0.01 0.3 0.5 y 0.0 0.0 1.0 z
    0.0 0.0 1.0
run          1000000
unfix       1
#-----Equilibration-----
fix          1 all npt temp 0.3 0.3 0.5 y 0.0 0.0 1.0 z
    0.0 0.0 1.0
run          500000
unfix       1
#-----Slow-Cooling-----
fix          1 all npt temp 0.3 0.01 0.5 y 0.0 0.0 1.0 z
    0.0 0.0 1.0
run          1000000
unfix       1
#-----Equilibration-----
fix          1 all npt temp 0.01 0.01 0.5 y 0.0 0.0 1.0 z
    0.0 0.0 1.0
run          1000000
unfix       1
read_data   data.lj_np_slab_restructured

```

7.1.5 Thermal cycling of Nano-sphere

```

#----- 3d LJ : Thermal Cycling -----
#-----Initialization -----
units       lj
dimension   3
boundary    f f f
atom_style  atomic
#-----System-Definition-----

```

```
read_data      data.lj_np_sphere
# ----- Define Interaction -----
pair_style     lj/cut 2.8
pair_modify    shift yes
pair_coeff     * * 1.0 1.0
#-----Neighbor list-----
neighbor       0.3 bin
neigh_modify   every 1 delay 0 check yes
#-----Print-output-----
restart        500 sphere_restart_1 sphere_restart_2
thermo_style   custom step ke pe etotal enthalpy temp pxx
               pyy pzz lx ly lz
thermo         50
#-----Dynamics-----
timestep       0.005
#-----Equilibration-----
fix            1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.01 0.5
run            500000
unfix         1
#-----Slow-Heating----
fix            1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.3 0.5
run            1000000
unfix         1
#-----Equilibration-----
fix            1 all nvt temp 0.3 0.3 0.5
run            500000
unfix         1
#-----Slow-Cooling-----
fix            1 all nvt temp 0.3 0.01 0.5
```

```

run          1000000
unfix       1
#-----Equilibration-----
fix         1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.01 0.5
run          1000000
unfix       1
read_data   data.lj_np_sphere_restructured

```

7.1.6 Thermal cycling of Hollow nano-shell

```

#----- 3d LJ : Thermal Cycling -----
#-----Initialization -----
units       lj
dimension   3
boundary    f f f
atom_style   atomic
#-----System-Definition-----
read_data   data.lj_np_hollow
# ----- Define Interaction -----
pair_style   lj/cut 2.8
pair_modify  shift yes
pair_coeff   * * 1.0 1.0
#-----Neighbor list-----
neighbor     0.3 bin
neigh_modify every 1 delay 0 check yes
#-----Print-output-----
restart      500 shell_restart_1 shell_restart_2
thermo_style custom step ke pe etotal enthalpy temp pxx
            pyy pzz lx ly lz
thermo       50

```

```

#-----Dynamics-----
timestep          0.005
#-----Equilibration-----
fix               1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.01 0.5
run               500000
unfix             1
#-----Slow-Heating----
fix               1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.25 0.5
run               1000000
unfix             1
#-----Equilibration-----
fix               1 all nvt temp 0.25 0.25 0.5
run               500000
unfix             1
#-----Slow-Cooling-----
fix               1 all nvt temp 0.25 0.01 0.5
run               1000000
unfix             1
#-----Equilibration-----
fix               1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.01 0.5
run               1000000
unfix             1
read_data         data.lj_np_shell_restructured

```

7.1.7 Production run of Nano-slab

```

#----- 3d LJ_nanoslab:Production -----
#-----Initialization -----
units             lj
dimension         3

```

```

boundary      f p p
atom_style    atomic
#-----System-Definition-----
read_data     data.lj_np_slab_restructured
# ----- Define Interaction -----
pair_style    lj/cut 2.8
pair_modify   shift yes
pair_coeff    * * 1.0 1.0
#-----Neighbor list-----
neighbor      0.3 bin
neigh_modify  every 1 delay 0 check yes
#-----Print-output-----
restart       500 slab_restart_1 slab_restart_2
thermo_style  custom step ke pe etotal enthalpy temp pxx
              pyy pzz lx ly lz
thermo       50
dump          1 all atom 300 lj_slab.dump
#-----Dynamics-----
timestep      0.005
fix           1 all npt temp 0.01 0.4 0.5 y 0.0 0.0 1.0 z
              0.0 0.0 1.0
run           3000000
unfix        1

```

7.1.8 Production run of Nano-sphere

```

#----- 3d LJ_nanosphere:Production -----
#-----Initialization -----
units        lj
dimension    3

```

```

boundary      f f f
atom_style    atomic
#-----System-Definition-----
read_data     data.lj_np_sphere_restructured
# ----- Define Interaction -----
pair_style    lj/cut 2.8
pair_modify   shift yes
pair_coeff    * * 1.0 1.0
#-----Neighbor list-----
neighbor      0.3 bin
neigh_modify  every 1 delay 0 check yes
#-----Print-output-----
restart       500 sphere_restart_1 sphere_restart_2
thermo_style  custom step ke pe etotal enthalpy temp pxx
              pyy pzz lx ly lz
thermo        50
dump          1 all atom 300 lj_sphere.dump
#-----Dynamics-----
timestep      0.005
fix           1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.4 0.5
run           3000000
unfix        1

```

7.1.9 Production run of Hollow nano-shell

```

#----- 3d LJ_nanosphere:Production -----
#-----Initialization -----
units         lj
dimension     3
boundary      f f f

```

```

atom_style      atomic
#-----System-Definition-----
read_data      data.lj_np_shell_restructured
# ----- Define Interaction -----
pair_style     lj/cut 2.8
pair_modify    shift yes
pair_coeff     * * 1.0 1.0
#-----Neighbor list-----
neighbor       0.3 bin
neigh_modify   every 1 delay 0 check yes
#-----Print-output----
restart        500 shell_restart_1 shell_restart_2
thermo_style   custom step ke pe etotal enthalpy temp pxx
               pyy pzz lx ly lz
thermo         50
dump           1 all atom 300 lj_shell.dump
#-----Dynamics-----
timestep       0.005
fix            1 all nvt temp 0.01 0.4 0.5
run            3000000
unfix         1

```

7.2 Data analysis codes in FORTRAN90

7.2.1 Local & cumulative density profile - Nano-slab

```

module types
  implicit none
  character(len=80) :: comment
  integer, parameter :: maxbin = 50000, n_c = 4, n_m = 80000

```

```

!Number of atoms
real, parameter :: pi = 4.0 * atan(1.0)
real, parameter :: ac_m = 1.0, si_m = 1.0
integer :: i, j, ierr, n_p, i_ts, i_p, i_t, n_ts, i_bin,
    max_j
integer :: hist(n_c,maxbin), hist_t(maxbin)
real :: xl, xh, yl, yh, zl, zh, x(n_m,n_c), y(n_m,n_c), z(
    n_m,n_c), y_dis
real :: x_min, y_min, z_min, r_min
real :: sum_x, sum_y, sum_z, sum_mass, x_si, y_si, z_si
real :: dens_MD, const, dens_si_MD, const_si, temp
real :: rlower, rupper, c_salt, c_si
real :: d_r, b_x, b_y, b_z, c_x, c_y, c_z, del_r
end module types

program coordinates
    use types

    open (unit=12, file="lj_slab_02.dump", & !input dump
        file from the simulation
            status="old", action="read", iostat=ierr)
    open (unit=15, file="dens_prof_02.dat", &
        status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
    open (unit=16, file="com_02.dat", &
        status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
    open (unit=17, file="size_02.dat", &
        status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)

    n_ts = 0
    do i = 1, n_c

```

```

do j = 1, maxbin
    hist(i,j) = 0
    hist_t(j) = 0
end do
end do
write(16,*) "# t_step, cm_x, cm_y, cm_z"
readfile : do
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
    if (ierr < 0) then
        print*, "end of file reached"
        exit readfile
    end if
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) i_ts
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) n_p
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) xl, xh
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) yl, yh
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) zl, zh
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
    n_ts = n_ts + 1
!   print*, "n_ts", n_ts
    b_x = (xh - xl)
    b_y = (yh - yl)
    b_z = (zh - zl)
    c_x = b_x / 2.0 + xl
    c_y = b_y / 2.0 + yl
    c_z = b_z / 2.0 + zl
    do i = 1, n_p

```

```

do j = 1, n_c
    x(i,j) = 0.0
end do
end do
! C center of mass calculation
sum_x = 0.0
sum_y = 0.0
sum_z = 0.0
sum_mass = 0.0
do i = 1, n_p
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) i_p, i_t, x(i,i_t), y(i,i_t),
        z(i,i_t)
    x(i,i_t) = x(i,i_t) * (xh - xl) + xl
    y(i,i_t) = y(i,i_t) * (yh - yl) + yl
    z(i,i_t) = z(i,i_t) * (zh - zl) + zl
!    if (i_t == 1) then
        sum_x = sum_x + si_m * x(i,i_t)
        sum_y = sum_y + si_m * y(i,i_t)
        sum_z = sum_z + si_m * z(i,i_t)
        sum_mass = sum_mass + si_m
!    end if
end do
x_si = sum_x / sum_mass
y_si = sum_y / sum_mass
z_si = sum_z / sum_mass
c_x = x_si
c_y = y_si
c_z = z_si
!    print*, 'n_ts', n_ts, ' X ', c_x, ' Y ', c_y, ' Z ',

```

```

c_z
write(16,*) n_ts, c_x, c_y, c_z
d_r = b_x / real(maxbin)
do i = 1, n_p
  do j = 1, n_c
    if (x(i,j) /= 0.0) then
      del_r = sqrt((x(i,j) - c_x)**2)
      i_bin = int (del_r / d_r) + 1
      if (i_bin <= maxbin) then
        hist(j,i_bin) = hist(j,i_bin) + 1
      end if
    end if
  end do
end do
end do readfile
close(unit=12)
do j = 1, maxbin - 1
  write(15,*) d_r*(real(j-1)-0.5), real(hist(1,j))/
    real(n_ts)
end do
print*, "I am here"
do i = 1, n_c
  do j = 2, maxbin - 1
    hist(i,j) = hist(i,j-1)+hist(i,j)
    hist_t(j) = hist_t(j) + hist(i,j)
!   print*, i, j, hist(i,j)/real(n_ts)
  end do
end do
do j = 1, maxbin - 1

```

```

print*, j, real(hist_t(j)/real(n_ts)), real(n_p)
if (real(hist_t(j)/real(n_ts)) .lt. real(n_p)) then
    write(17,*) d_r*(real(j)-0.5), real(hist_t(j)/real(
        n_ts))
else
    write(17,*) d_r*(real(j-1)-0.5), 0.0
end if
end do
close(unit=17)
close(unit=15)
end program coordinates

```

7.2.2 Local & cumulative density profile - Nano-sphere & hollow nano-shell

```

module types
    implicit none
    character(len=80) :: comment
    integer, parameter :: maxbin = 10000, n_c = 1, n_m =
        134000 !Number of atoms
    real, parameter :: pi = 4.0 * atan(1.0)
    real, parameter :: ac_m = 12.0107, si_m = 12.0107, lj_m =
        1.0
    integer :: i, j, ierr, n_p, i_ts, i_p, i_t, n_ts, i_bin,
        max_j
    integer :: hist(n_c,maxbin)
    real :: xl, xh, yl, yh, zl, zh, x(n_m,n_c), y(n_m,n_c), z(
        n_m,n_c), y_dis
    real :: x_min, y_min, z_min, r_min
    real :: sum_x, sum_y, sum_z, sum_mass, x_si, y_si, z_si

```

```

real :: dens_MD, const, dens_si_MD, const_si, temp
real :: rlower, rupper, c_salt, c_si
real :: d_r, b_x, b_y, b_z, c_x, c_y, c_z, del_r
end module types

program coordinates
  use types

  open (unit=12, file="lj_sphere_02.dump", & !Input dump
        file from LAMMPS
        status="old", action="read", iostat=ierr)
  open (unit=15, file="dens_prof_02.dat", &
        status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
  open (unit=16, file="com_02.dat", &
        status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
  open (unit=17, file="size_02.dat", &
        status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
!  print*, 'Temp [K]:'
!  read*, temp
  n_ts = 0
  do i = 1, n_c
    do j = 1, maxbin
      hist(i,j) = 0
    end do
  end do
  write(16,*) "# t_step, cm_x, cm_y, cm_z"
  readfile : do
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
    if (ierr < 0) then

```

```
        print*, "end of file reached"
        exit readfile
end if
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) i_ts
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) n_p
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) xl, xh
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) yl, yh
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) zl, zh
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
n_ts = n_ts + 1
!   print*, "n_ts", n_ts
b_x = (xh - xl)
b_y = (yh - yl)
b_z = (zh - zl)
c_x = b_x / 2.0 + xl
c_y = b_y / 2.0 + yl
c_z = b_z / 2.0 + zl
!   print*, c_x, c_y, c_z
if (abs(xl) <= abs(xh)) then
    x_min = abs(xl)
else
    x_min = abs(xh)
end if
if (abs(yl) <= abs(yh)) then
    y_min = abs(yl)
else
    y_min = abs(yh)
```

```
end if
if (abs(zl) <= abs(zh)) then
    z_min = abs(zl)
else
    z_min = abs(zh)
end if
if(x_min < y_min) then
    r_min = x_min
else
    r_min = y_min
end if
if(r_min > z_min) then
    r_min = z_min
end if
do i = 1, n_p
    do j = 1, n_c
        x(i,j) = 0.0
    end do
end do
! C center of mass calculation
sum_x = 0.0
sum_y = 0.0
sum_z = 0.0
sum_mass = 0.0
do i = 1, n_p
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) i_p, i_t, x(i,i_t), y(i,i_t),
        z(i,i_t)
    x(i,i_t) = x(i,i_t) * (xh - xl) + xl
    y(i,i_t) = y(i,i_t) * (yh - yl) + yl
```

```

        z(i,i_t) = z(i,i_t) * (zh - zl) + zl
!   print*, i_p, x(i,i_t), y(i,i_t), z(i,i_t)
        if (i_t == 1) then
            sum_x = sum_x + si_m * x(i,i_t)
            sum_y = sum_y + si_m * y(i,i_t)
            sum_z = sum_z + si_m * z(i,i_t)
            sum_mass = sum_mass + si_m
        end if
    end do

x_si = sum_x / sum_mass
y_si = sum_y / sum_mass
z_si = sum_z / sum_mass
c_x = x_si
c_y = y_si
c_z = z_si
print*, 'n_ts', n_ts, ' X ', c_x, ' Y ', c_y, ' Z ', c_z
write(16,*) n_ts, c_x, c_y, c_z
d_r = b_x / real(maxbin)
do i = 1, n_p
    do j = 1, n_c
        if (x(i,j) /= 0.0) then
            del_r = sqrt((x(i,j) - c_x)**2 + (y(i,j) - c_y
                )**2 + (z(i,j) - c_z)**2)
            i_bin = int (del_r / d_r) + 1
            if (i_bin <= maxbin) then
                hist(j,i_bin) = hist(j,i_bin) + 1
            end if
        end if
    end do
end do

```

```

        end do
end do readfile
close(unit=12)
print*, "I am here"
dens_ac = 1.08
dens_ac = dens_ac / lj_m

! const = 4.0 * pi * dens_MD / 3.0
const_ac = 4.0 * pi * dens_ac / 3.0
write(15,*)"# dist      density"
do j = 1, maxbin - 1
    rlower = real(j-1) * d_r
    rupper = rlower + d_r
    c_ac = const_ac * (rupper**3 - rlower**3)
    !print*, real(hist(1,j))/real(n_ts)
    write(15,*) d_r*(real(j)-0.5), real(hist(1,j))/real(
        n_ts)/c_ac
end do

do j = 2, maxbin - 1
    hist(1,j) = hist(1,j-1)+hist(1,j)
end do

! print*, "I am here"
do j = 1, maxbin - 1
    if (real(hist(1,j))/real(n_ts)) .lt. real(n_p-1)) then
        write(17,*) d_r*(real(j)-0.5), real(hist(1,j))/real(
            n_ts))
    else
        write(17,*) d_r*(real(j-1)-0.5), 0.0
    !
        print*, "I am here"

```

```

        end if
    end do
    close(unit=17)
    close(unit=15)
end program coordinates

```

7.2.3 Amplitude of atomic vibrations - Nano-slab

```

module types
    implicit none
    character(len=80) :: comment
    integer, parameter :: maxbin = 100, n_m = 100000, n_s =
        1000 ! Number of surface atoms
    integer, parameter :: n_c = 500
    real, parameter :: pi = 4.0 * atan(1.0)
    integer :: i, j, ierr, n_p, i_ts, i_p, i_t, n_ts, i_bin,
        i_surf
    integer :: hist(n_c,maxbin)
    integer :: i_tlin
    real:: r_min(3), r_max(3), r_lind(3,n_m), d_r(3), sum(3),
        r_l(n_c,3,n_m)
    real :: xl, xh, yl, yh, zl, zh, x(n_m,n_c), y(n_m,n_c), z(
        n_m,n_c), y_dis
    real :: x_min, y_min, z_min, x_surf(n_m,n_s), sum_c(n_m),
        ssum !, r_min
    integer :: i_part(n_c)
end module types

program coordinates
    use types

```

```

open (unit=15, file="lind_x_3_bulk.dat", &
      status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
open (unit=17, file="lind_y_3_bulk.dat", &
      status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
open (unit=18, file="lind_z_3_bulk.dat", &
      status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)

open (unit=13, file="trajectory_x.dat", &
      status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
open (unit=14, file="trajectory_y.dat", &
      status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
open (unit=16, file="trajectory_z.dat", &
      status="unknown", action="write", iostat=ierr)
!-----
open (unit=12, file="lj_slab.dump", & ! Input dump file
      from LAMMPS
      status="old", action="read", iostat=ierr)
i_tlin = 0
readfile : do
  read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
  if (ierr < 0) then
    print*, "end of file reached"
    exit readfile
  end if
  read(12,*,iostat=ierr) i_ts
  read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
  read(12,*,iostat=ierr) n_p
  read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment

```

```

read(12,*,iostat=ierr) xl, xh
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) yl, yh
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) zl, zh
read(12,*,iostat=ierr) comment
!      n_ts = n_ts + 1
i_tlin = i_tlin + 1
i_surf = 0
do i = 1, n_p
    read(12,*,iostat=ierr) i_p, i_t, x(i,i_t), y(i,i_t),
        z(i,i_t)
!   if (i_t==3) then ! upper surface
    if (i_t==3) then ! .and. x(i,i_t) < 0.415) then !
        lower surface ! i_t is the index of the atoms -
            depends on simulation details
        i_surf = i_surf + 1
        r_l(i_surf,1,i_tlin) = x(i,i_t) * (xh - xl) + xl
        r_l(i_surf,2,i_tlin) = y(i,i_t) * (yh - yl) + yl
        r_l(i_surf,3,i_tlin) = z(i,i_t) * (zh - zl) + zl
    end if
end do
print*, "i_lind=", i_tlin
end do readfile
close(unit=12)
print*, "End of reading"
!-----
print*, "i_lind=", i_tlin
print*, "i_surf", i_surf
do k = 1, i_surf
    do i = 1, i_tlin

```

```

do j = 1, 3
    r_lind(j,i) = r_l(k,j,i)
end do
end do
do i = 1, 3
    r_min(i) = r_lind(i,1)
    r_max(i) = r_lind(i,1)
end do
do i = 2, i_tlin
    do j = 1, 3
        if (r_lind(j,i) < r_min(j)) r_min(j) = r_lind(j,i
        )
        if (r_lind(j,i) > r_max(j)) r_max(j) = r_lind(j,i
        )
    end do
end do
print*, "particle", k
do i = 1, 3
    print*, "min =", r_min(i)
    print*, "max =", r_max(i)
end do
write(13,*) '# n_ts, x i_part', k
write(14,*) '# n_ts, y i_part', k
write(16,*) '# n_ts, z i_part', k
do i = 1, i_tlin !n_ts
    do j = 1, 3
        r_lind(j,i) = r_lind(j,i) - r_min(j)
    end do
    write(13,*) i, r_lind(1,i)

```

```

        write(14,*) i, r_lind(2,i)
        write(16,*) i, r_lind(3,i)
    end do
write(13,*) "    "
write(14,*) "    "
write(16,*) "    "
do i = 1, 3
    d_r(i) = abs(r_max(i) - r_min(i)) / real(maxbin-1)
end do
do i = 1, 3
    do j = 1, maxbin
        hist(i,j) = 0
    end do
end do
do i = 1, i_tlin !n_ts
    do j = 1, 3
        i_bin = int (r_lind(j,i) / d_r(j)) + 1
        if (i_bin <= maxbin) then
            hist(j,i_bin) = hist(j,i_bin) + 1
        end if
    end do
end do
do i = 1, 3
    sum(i) = 0.0
end do
write(15,*) "# x, hist_x, i_part", k
write(17,*) "# y, hist_y, i_part", k
write(18,*) "# z, hist_z, i_part", k
do i = 1, maxbin !- 1

```

```
write(15,*) d_r(1)*(real(i)-0.5)+r_min(1), real(hist
    (1,i))
write(17,*) d_r(2)*(real(i)-0.5), real(hist(2,i))
write(18,*) d_r(3)*(real(i)-0.5), real(hist(3,i))
do j = 1, 3
    sum(j) = sum(j) + real(hist(j,i))
end do
end do
write(15,*) "    "
write(17,*) "    "
write(18,*) "    "
print*, "# config =", sum(1), sum(2), sum(3)
end do
print*, "end"
close(unit=13)
close(unit=14)
close(unit=16)
close(unit=15)
close(unit=17)
close(unit=18)
end program coordinates
```
